

Automated Citation Verification in Scientific Literature Using Large Language Models

Insa Kristin Belter

Master Thesis

for the acquisition of the academic degree Master of Science (M.Sc.)

Course of Studies: Computer Science

Department of Computer Science
University of Applied Sciences Mannheim

2025-11-30

Tutors

Prof. Dr. Ivo Wolf

Prof. Dr. rer. nat. Kai Eckert

Belter, Insa Kristin:

Automatisierte Verifikation von Wissenschaftlichen Zitaten unter Verwendung von Large Language Models / Insa Kristin Belter. –

Master-Thesis, Mannheim: Technische Hochschule Mannheim, 2025. 130 Seiten.

Belter, Insa Kristin:

Automated Citation Verification in Scientific Literature Using Large Language Models / Insa Kristin Belter. –

Master Thesis, Mannheim: University of Applied Sciences Mannheim, 2025. 130 pages.

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Abstract

Automated Citation Verification in Scientific Literature Using Large Language Models

Despite the importance of accurate citations for scientific literature quality, citation errors persist across scholarly publications. This thesis investigates the potential of zero-shot in-context learning with large language models (LLMs) for automated citation verification, specifically examining how linguistic features of citation statements influence classification performance. An existing dataset of 250 citation-reference pairs was re-annotated to extract syntactic and semantic citation statement features. Building on prior work, a classification pipeline was implemented with systematic optimizations of identified configuration parameters. Although notable differences were observed when comparing the classification performance across subsets grouped by annotation attribute values, they lack statistical significance under multiple testing correction. Nevertheless, achieving a balanced accuracy of 85.6%, this thesis demonstrates the promising potential of LLM-based citation verification while pointing out areas for future improvement.

Abstrakt

Automatisierte Verifikation von Wissenschaftlichen Zitaten unter Verwendung von Large Language Models

Trotz der Wichtigkeit korrekter Zitationen für die Qualität wissenschaftlicher Literatur, sind Zitationsfehler in zahlreichen Fachpublikationen zu finden. Diese Masterarbeit untersucht das Potenzial von Zero-Shot In-Context Learning mit Large Language Models (LLMs) zur automatisierten Zitationsüberprüfung und analysiert dabei, inwiefern sprachliche Eigenschaften von Zitaten die Klassifikationsleistung beeinflussen. Ein bestehender Datensatz mit 250 Zitat-Referenz-Paaren wurde um Annotationen erweitert, um semantische und syntaktische Zitatmerkmale zu erfassen. Aufbauend auf vorheriger Forschung wurde ein Klassifikationsprozess implementiert, welcher anhand identifizierter Konfigurationsparameter systematisch optimiert wurde. Es wurden Unterschiede in der Klassifikationsleistung zwischen Zitationsgruppen mit verschiedenen Attributausprägungen festgestellt, welche jedoch nach Korrektur für multiples Testen nicht statistisch signifikant sind. Mit einer Balanced Accuracy von 85,6 % zeigt die Arbeit dennoch das Potenzial von LLM-basierter Zitationsverifikation auf und nennt Verbesserungsmöglichkeiten für zukünftige Forschungsansätze.

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List of Abbreviations

AI artificial intelligence

CoT Chain-of-Thought

DOI Digital Object Identifier

GPT generative pre-trained transformer

GROBID GeneRation Of Bibliographic Data

ICL in-context learning

IEEE Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers

JSON JavaScript Object Notation

LM language model

LLM large language model

ML machine learning

MoE Mixture of Experts

NLI natural language inference

NLP natural language processing

PBTE paper body text extraction

PDF Portable Document Format

QA question answering

QG question generation

RAG retrieval-augmented generation

RNN recurrent neural network

RLHF reinforcement learning from human feedback

TEI Text Encoding Initiative

XML Extensible Markup Language

Chapter 1

Introduction

This introduction outlines the purpose of this thesis by providing motivation for the task of automated citation verification, defining the research question, and describing scope limitations.

1.1 Motivation

Citations are an important practice to substantiate statements within scientific papers, make cross-references, and ensure an overall high quality of academic publications. Nevertheless, there are many occurrences of erroneous citations within published works [1], with an error rate of 25% reported by Smith and Cumberledge [2].

A citation error occurs when a paper is cited within a citation statement, but the cited source either is non-existent, or the statement is not substantiated by the paper, or even refuted by it. Citation errors could, for example, result from insufficient understanding of the cited paper or a lack of training in citation methodology [1]. Detecting such errors is a time-consuming task during the reviewing process of a scientific paper, as it involves manually accessing the referenced paper, finding the relevant text passages, and understanding them to the point that the citation can be verified or falsified.

There are several free or proprietary tools available to assist in scientific writing by finding relevant papers to cite (*Google Scholar*¹, *Sourcely*²), checking for plagiarism (*Grammarly*³, *Scribbr*⁴), generating citations (*Scribbr*⁵), or even checking if a referenced paper is retracted, old, or unverified (*Trinka*⁶). Nonetheless, within the research for this thesis, no tool was found that can automatically verify citation statements against the textual contents of referenced source papers.

¹<https://scholar.google.com/>

²<https://www.sourcely.net/>

³<https://www.grammarly.com/plagiarism-checker>

⁴<https://www.scribbr.com/plagiarism-checker/>

⁵<https://www.scribbr.com/citation/generator/>

⁶<https://www.trinka.ai/features/citation-checker>

The inspiration for this thesis is the idea of a fully automated citation verification tool which automatically detects citations within a paper (the *citation paper*), downloads the papers referenced in the citations (*reference papers*) to verify the citation claims, and then outputs detected citation errors. As analyzing, developing, and evaluating all the parts needed for such a tool is out of scope, this thesis focuses on the core part of such a tool: automated citation verification. Deciding whether a citation statement is substantiated by the referenced source or contains a citation error is a classification task that could be approached with several different methods – for example, traditional rule-based methods, machine learning (ML) algorithms, or different deep learning techniques. With the rising capabilities of large language models (LLMs), one of the most popular methods of recent years is in-context learning (ICL), where a prompt with a task description and optionally a few examples of already labeled data is given to an LLM, which attempts to solve the given problem only based on this context information without any additional fine-tuning to the specific task [3–5].

At the time of research, only one paper was found that researches the potential of applying a zero-shot ICL technique to the classification task of automated citation verification: *Detecting Reference Errors in Scientific Literature with Large Language Models* by Zhang and Abernethy [6]. Within their research, they create a dataset of statement-reference pairs, labeled by the substantiation amount of the citation [6]. Their main research focus was to compare the LLM classification performance for multiple prompts that differ in the amount of textual information that was extracted from the reference paper [6].

An interesting relationship that was not researched by Zhang and Abernethy is the impact of the citation statement itself on the classification performance. There are many different purposes of citing which can lead to syntactic and semantic differences between citation statements of scientific publications. Creating a suitable annotation scheme to differentiate these citation statement features and evaluating their effects on the citation verification performance in the described zero-shot ICL setting is the main research focus of this thesis.

1.2 Research Question

This section introduces the research question which will be evaluated in depth in the following sections of this thesis.

As introduced in section 1.1, the main focus of this thesis is on automated citation verification, meaning that a classifier should decide whether a citation statement contains any citation errors or is fully substantiated by the reference paper. This task can be defined as a classification task with two labels: Substantiated and Unsubstantiated, making the perfor-

mance on the task measurable using classification metrics including accuracy, balanced accuracy, precision, recall and F1-Score which are explained in section 3.2.

There are many factors that could influence the classification performance, starting with the applied classification method. This thesis researches the potential and limitations of in-context learning with a zero-shot approach, meaning that an LLM is given a prompt that explains the citation verification task in detail, and context information, including the citation statement and additional textual information extracted from the citation and the reference paper.

Unlike in a few-shot setting, in a zero-shot setting, the classifier LLM does not receive any labeled examples for the task as part of the prompt. Although few-shot learning can outperform zero-shot learning approaches on a variety of natural language processing (NLP) tasks [3], it depends on a representative selection of labeled examples. Since there is a high variety of citation statement features analyzed within this thesis, using a zero-shot approach eliminates potential bias from example selection and provides a more controlled experiment environment to isolate the effects of the different features on classification performance.

Citations are used within scientific publications for a wide variety of purposes [7–9], leading to syntactic and semantic linguistic differences between citation statements. For example, a reference paper might be cited because it directly supports or contradicts the findings of the citation paper, or it might be only tangentially related, where the citation serves to reference a broader topic or simply acknowledges related work in the field. At the same time, citations vary in their structural composition: they may appear as single standalone references or as part of a list enumerating multiple sources with the purpose to substantiate multiple claims at once or to aggregate the paper findings to collectively substantiate a single claim.

This variety in citation statement features presents distinct challenges for automated verification, potentially influencing both the complexity and performance of the classification task. An in-depth evaluation of the impacts of linguistic features on classification performance could provide deeper, more fine-grained insights into the limitations of LLMs, which could potentially be applied to similar classification tasks.

These considerations motivate the following research question of causality:

How do syntactic and semantic features of citation statements influence the citation verification performance of a large language model in a zero-shot in-context learning classification setting?

1.3 Limitations

The scope and interpretation of this thesis is influenced by several limitations, which are outlined in this section.

First, the research landscape in LLM applications is rapidly evolving, with frequent releases of increasingly capable models. Additionally, some recent research results relevant to this field are only published on preprint platforms such as arXiv, which does not require peer reviews, as the time constraints of traditional journal publication processes lead to publication delays. For practical reasons, only publications available up to April 2025 were considered for the dataset selection and re-annotation, and no LLMs released after July 2025 could be included in the experiments of this thesis.

Second, there is a lack of comparative baselines for this specific task, as only one prior study was found that specifically applies ICL to citation verification using a dataset derived from actual occurrences of citation errors in scientific publications [6]. The most similar research in the field focuses on claim verification, where negative claims are artificially crafted from positive examples [10, 11]. Without an established benchmark for citation verification, contextualizing the findings and assessing performance relative to different classification approaches remains limited.

Third, the scope of this thesis was constrained by limited time and financial resources. Evaluating proprietary LLMs incurs usage costs, which restricted the number of different LLMs, prompt variations, and configuration parameter variations that could be tested. Computational constraints also limited model selection: while university server resources enabled the inclusion of some open-weight models in the experiments, larger models that exceeded the available storage and memory capacity could not be evaluated.

Finally, the re-annotation process of the dataset could not be performed or reviewed by domain experts. While most labels remained unchanged from the original dataset by Zhang and Abernethy [6], Partially Substantiated citations were relabeled to create a binary classification setting, as detailed in section 4.1.2. Although efforts were made to ensure consistency and reliability, expert verification would likely improve internal validity, particularly for ambiguous citation cases.

Despite these limitations, the findings of this thesis provide valuable insights into the relationship between citation statement features and automated verification performance, contributing to the understanding of LLM capabilities in citation verification tasks and laying groundwork for the development of standardized benchmarks in this research field.

Chapter 2

Related Work

This chapter provides an overview of existing literature relevant to automated citation verification and the linguistic analysis of citation statements, which is essential for identifying research gaps, establishing the methodological foundation, and positioning the contributions of this thesis within the current scientific discourse.

First, section 2.1 examines the prevalence and underlying causes of citation errors in scientific publications, establishing the motivation for approaches of automated citation error detection. Section 2.2 reviews the limited current research on automated citation verification, positioning it within the broader context of the related field of claim verification. Section 2.3 reviews existing annotation schemes for categorizing citation statement features, which provided the conceptual foundation for the annotation scheme developed in this thesis. Finally, section 2.4 presents relevant datasets for citation verification and claim verification tasks that were considered for the research process of this thesis.

2.1 Citation Errors

Citations have been used in scientific papers for centuries as a way to reference related research work, benefiting both author and reader [1]. While the general assumption is that most citations within published papers are accurate, numerous examples of citation errors exist, with documented cases dating back to at least the 19th century [1].

Smith and Cumberledge's research provides empirical evidence for these individual cases through a systematic study on citation errors [2]. They collected 50 random citations from the 100 most cited articles of each of the five general science journals with the highest impact factors in 2017 [2]. The citations were distributed between two reviewers, who classified each citation for its level of substantiation by the referenced source [2]. Over all the citations, only 75% are fully substantiated and 25% contain citation errors [2]. The authors acknowledge that the two reviewers are not experts in any of the scientific fields being discussed [2], which could impact the reliability of the results. Nevertheless, their findings suggest a substantial proportion of citation errors in current scientific literature.

Smith and Cumberledge differentiate between *citation errors* and *quotation errors*. Citation errors include missing or redundant citations, incorrect citation styles, or false metadata on the cited source. Quotation errors occur whenever the cited source fails to substantiate the claim from the cited statement [2]. As the term *quotation* is commonly used to refer to the direct repeating of words written or said by someone else [12], this wording could lead to confusion because direct quotes cannot result in *quotation errors* by the definition of Smith and Cumberledge. For this reason, and because the dataset used in this thesis does not distinguish between these two error types, the term *citation error* is used to refer to all mentioned error cases.

There are various theories regarding the underlying causes of citation errors. Sweetland proposes that errors may result from insufficient understanding of the cited paper, potentially due to language barriers or inconsistent citation standards [1]. Additionally, he identifies inadequate training in citation methodology and the fragmentation of quality control responsibilities across the publishing process as contributing factors [1]. Kuznetsov et al. support this perspective and emphasize the increasing complexity and time-consuming nature of peer reviews [13]. They report that submission rates are rising while identifying qualified reviewers with sufficient expertise in specific topics is becoming increasingly difficult [13].

Although Kuznetsov et al. suggest the integration of LLMs into NLP-assisted peer review processes [13], research by Walters et al. demonstrates that the rising popularity of LLMs can also pose risks to citation quality in scientific publications [14]. They analyzed citation errors within scientific content generated by ChatGPT, using two different versions (ChatGPT-3.5 and ChatGPT-4) to produce short literature reviews on multidisciplinary topics and subsequently evaluating the correctness of the generated citations [14].

Their analysis focused on identifying hallucinated citations (by them called *fabricated* citations) that do not exist, as well as other citation errors such as incorrect author names [14]. These results reveal that while ChatGPT-4 citations are less prone to citation errors than ChatGPT-3.5 citations, 18% of ChatGPT-4 citations are still fabricated, and 24% of the non-fabricated citations contain other citation errors [14].

Collectively, this body of research underscores the need for reliable citation error detection solutions.

2.2 Citation Verification

Detecting citation errors as part of automated citation verification is closely related to the scientific NLP field of natural language inference (NLI), which evaluates whether one textual statement logically follows from or is supported by another [15]. As part of the

SNLI and *e-SNLI* datasets [15, 16], two large annotated text corpora for learning **NLI**, this classification task is defined as follows: The relation between two sentences, the premise and the hypothesis, should be classified into three categories: *Entailment* if the hypothesis logically follows from the premise, *Contradiction* if the hypothesis and premise are contradictory, or *Neutral* if there is neither entailment nor contradiction between the two statements [15].

These two **NLI** datasets were followed by several others with corresponding **NLI** metrics, many of which are included in the factual consistency evaluation framework *TRUE*, introduced by Honovich et al. [17]. Within their research paper, Honovich et al. compare different *faithfulness metrics* for automated factual consistency checking on a standardized collection of existing texts from diverse **NLP** tasks, like summarization and fact verification [17]. Next to **NLI** metrics like their self-developed model *ANLI* [17] and **QG-QA**-based metrics (question generation (**QG**) and question answering (**QA**)) such as Q^2 [18], they apply n-gram-based metrics such as *ROUGE* [19] and similarity-based metrics like the *BERTScore* [20]. Honovich et al. included eleven datasets with human annotations in their evaluation framework and converted all dataset labels to binary labels, describing whether the target text is factually consistent with the given grounding text or not. Their results show that large-scale **NLI** and **QG-QA**-based metric approaches perform better than the n-gram-based or similarity-based approaches across multiple tasks and datasets, especially when combined.

While no research papers were found that apply these faithfulness metrics directly to a corpus of actual citations from scientific literature, some research has been done on using them to evaluate the quality of **LLM**-generated text containing citations [21, 22]. Gao et al. [21] introduced the *ALCE* benchmark, which combines questions and retrieval corpora from three datasets (*ASQA* [23], *QAMPARI* [24], and *ELI5* [25]) and requires the building of end-to-end **LLM** systems that can generate answers to the questions including citations from the retrieval corpora [21]. While the citation correctness on two of the three datasets can be evaluated by checking how many of the provided short entity answers are contained in the generated response, summarization evaluation techniques are applied for the *ELI5* dataset to generate sub-claims using *InstructGPT* [21]. Afterward, *TRUE* is used to evaluate whether the generated text entails these claims [21].

Zhang et al. [22] also compare the effectiveness of different faithfulness metrics for the evaluation of **LLM**-generated text with citations, but additionally include an **ICL** approach in the comparison by prompting a general-domain **LLM** to perform a faithfulness evaluation. Their analyzed classification task consists of determining the level of support that a citation from a retrieval-augmented **LLM** provides for a given statement using three labels: Full Support (FS), Partial Support (PS) and No Support (NS) [22]. The labels {FS, PS,

NS} are mapped to the values {0, 1, 2} to then measure the alignment between faithfulness metric scores and human annotations by applying correlation analysis and classification evaluation [22]. Their results indicate that similarity-based metrics like *BERTScore* [20] and entailment-based (NLI) metrics such as *FactCC* [26] – which all result from LLMs that were specifically fine-tuned on different datasets for the task of natural language inference [20, 22] – outperform the ICL LLM-based classification approach [22]. Zhang et al. do not provide details on how the prompts were crafted and whether multiple prompts were compared in the research process. The included prompts contain a very short explanation of the task without giving precise definitions of the different support levels. At the same time, the LLM should perform the additional step of mapping the label to a discrete score, which might be challenging due to limitations of LLMs with regard to interpreting numbers within a linguistic context [27].

Substantially better classification performance on a zero-shot ICL methodology for a similar, citation-related task is reported by Zhang and Abernethy [6]. They evaluated the ability of LLMs to detect citation errors in existing papers, which is analogous to the classification task of this thesis. The research focus of Zhang and Abernethy is on detecting the impact of the amount of information on the reference paper that is provided to the classifier LLM as part of the prompt. This means that either only the title, the title and the abstract, or title, abstract and excerpts from the reference paper are included in the prompt. The excerpts were selected by applying a 3-step retrieval-augmented generation (RAG) mechanism: extracting the full text from the PDF, splitting it into 256-token chunks with 20-token overlaps, and then extracting the three chunks that are most similar to the input statement [6]. The main results of the paper are that providing more information does not necessarily increase the classification performance [6], suggesting that the LLM might use parametric knowledge from its training process. The classification explanations did not contain significant signs of hallucinating, though [6]. However, the integrated RAG approach does seem to have beneficial effects on the classification task when only classifying between Substantiated and Unsubstantiated (instead of distinguishing between Fully Substantiated and Partially Substantiated), though. In this binary classification setting, the accuracy of the models that were given the extracted reference paper excerpts is higher than if only title and abstract were provided. Out of the three compared LLMs, GPT-4 Turbo achieves the best overall label accuracy with around 86% on the binary evaluation [6].

2.3 Citation Annotation Schemes

To evaluate the influence of linguistic citation statement features on citation verification performance, the relevant syntactic and semantic features must be systematically catego-

rized. While no annotation scheme was found that was designed specifically for categorizing citations based on their suitability for LLM-based citation verification, this section showcases a selection of the annotation schemes found as part of the literature research which inspired the annotation scheme designed for this thesis.

One of the first annotation schemes for categorizing citations was published in 1975 by Moravcsik and Murugesan [7]. Their proposed annotation scheme consists of four categorical dimensions, each defined by opposing attribute pairs [7]:

1. *conceptual* (applying a theory) vs. *operational* (applying a technical method)
2. *organic* (reference is needed for understanding) vs. *perfunctory* (citation for general acknowledgment)
3. *evolutionary* (reference was used as basis) vs. *juxtapositional* (reference is cited as alternative)
4. *confirmative* (citation claims that reference is correct) vs. *negational* (citation disputes the correctness of the reference)

This scheme was used as the inspiration for another often-cited annotation scheme published in 2006 by Teufel et al. [8]. It comprises twelve categories which are organized into four top-level classifications: *weakness*, *contrast*, *positive*, and *neutral* [8]. The main focus of the proposed scheme is to annotate how the author relates the citation statement to the cited reference and which purpose the citation serves in the overall argumentative structure of the text [8].

Multiple other citation function annotation schemes can be found, which are mostly extensions of the schemes from Moravcsik et al. and Teufel et al. but vary in their focus and level of detail due to different intended applications of the schemes. Dong et al. [28], for example, aimed to create a more simple annotation scheme consisting of four citation functions, which they claim to be the “most general and mutually exclusive citation functions” [28], in order to maximize the performance of their supervised classification models [28]. Taşkın et al., on the other hand, introduced a fine-grained, multi-layered annotation scheme designed to automatically classify Turkish citations [29]. Unlike other annotation schemes, theirs encompasses not only semantic citation functions – such as twelve subcategories for citation purpose (e.g., Comparison or Mentioning Pioneers) and three distinctions of citation meaning (Positive, Negative, Neutral) – but also syntactic variations between citation statements, including whether multiple citations occur within the same sentence and how often the same reference is cited within the text.

2.4 Relevant Datasets

This section gives an overview of the most relevant datasets that were considered during the research process of this thesis.

A very promising dataset for a variety of different NLP tasks is the *Dr. Inventor* corpus by Fisas et al. [30], which is a corpus consisting of 10,777 sentences from 40 scientific articles. Each sentence is annotated by associating it with the overall argumentative structure of the article. The purpose of citations contained in these sentences is annotated using a custom multi-layered annotation scheme with six top categories [30]. Lauscher et al. extended this corpus with additional argument annotations that point out the argumentative relations between the sentences of the corpus [31]. The *Dr. Inventor* corpus can, for example, be used to train models for automated sentence classification or automated text summarization [30], but without further annotation, it is not suited for the task of automated citation error detection because the included citations were not yet verified against their reference papers.

An often-cited claim verification dataset is the *FEVER* dataset created by Thorne et al. [32]. Citation verification is closely related to the field of claim verification, where the task is to verify atomic scientific claims that are often artificially crafted from large text corpora. The 185,445 claims included in the *FEVER* dataset were manually extracted from *Wikipedia*⁷ articles by human annotators. Examples of unsubstantiated claims were produced by mutating the extracted substantiated claims through altering the meaning or negating the sentences, avoiding trivial negations such as simply adding the word *not* to the sentence [32].

Another claim verification dataset is *SciFact* from Wadden et al. [10], which contains 1,409 scientific claims to be verified against a corpus of 5,183 abstracts containing evidence. Instead of extracting claims from Wikipedia, actual scientific citation statements were taken as the basis for the claims in *SciFact*. The citations were extracted from the *S2ORC* corpus of scientific articles [33] by drawing random samples from a selection of journals [10]. Afterward, human annotators rephrased the citation statements into atomic scientific claims and assigned classification labels for whether the claims are supported or refuted by the included evidence. By ensuring that a claim contains exactly one atomic statement, each claim is verifiable from a single source [10]. Citations that do not contain clear statements about scientific findings were skipped by the annotators [10]. These selection and pre-processing methods reduce the complexity of the classification task because the sentence structures and the number of claims per sentence do not vary as much

⁷<https://www.wikipedia.org/>

between different dataset entries. Erroneous claims – within this dataset labeled as *Refuted* – were manually crafted from supported claims by having human annotators negate the claims [10], similar to the *FEVER* dataset.

A recently released dataset called *SciClaimHunt* from Kumar et al. is similar to *SciFact* in its dataset structure but contains substantially more dataset entries, with over 100,000 claims [11]. The dataset was constructed by using LLMs to generate positive and negative claims based on manually extracted positive claims from human annotators [11]. Additional positive claims were generated by prompting an LLM with existing claim-reference pairs as examples and then providing it new references to extract further claims from [11]. The negative claims were generated using four different methods [11]:

1. negating positive claims using few-shot in-context learning
2. mismatching positive claims with different research papers
3. altering cardinal and numerical values from positive claims
4. switching semantically similar scientific keywords using the Knowledge Base Informed Negations approach introduced by Wright et al. [34]

The combination of these methods lead to more variety in error types compared to the *SciFact* dataset, but the citation errors were still artificially crafted.

The only dataset found as part of the conducted research that consists of actual examples of citation errors from published scientific literature is the dataset constructed by Zhang and Abernethy [6]. Their general-domain dataset, containing 250 citation statement-reference pairs from journal articles, was created by extending a collection of existing statement-reference pair datasets [6]. Additional examples of citation errors were found by cross-referencing retracted papers from the *Retraction Watch Database*⁸ with comments about problematic citations on the platform *PubPeer*⁹, where researchers can give feedback on other publications [6]. All of the statements were reviewed, and information about the citing paper and the reference paper was added, such as DOI, title, and abstract [6]. The citation statements of their dataset were manually classified into Fully Substantiated, Partially Substantiated and Unsubstantiated [6]. This is a typical labeling approach for citations, as similar labels are used by Smith and Cumberledge [2] and Zhang et al. [22] (*Supported* instead of *Substantiated*). Although Zhang and Abernethy claim that their dataset is “expert-annotated” [6], they do not give exact details on the annotation process of verifying the added statement-reference pairs, making it difficult to fully evaluate the quality of their dataset.

⁸<http://retractiondatabase.org/>

⁹<https://pubpeer.com/>

Chapter 3

Theory

This chapter provides the theoretical foundation for the methodological approaches and evaluation techniques employed in this thesis. First, section 3.1 introduces **LLMs**, covering their evolution from early rule-based systems to modern transformer architectures, an overview of the development of current OpenAI **GPT** and Meta Llama models, and their limitations and ethical considerations. Section 3.2 provides classification fundamentals, including evaluation metrics for both binary and multiclass settings, and a short introduction to selective classification. Finally, section 3.3 presents statistical significance testing methods relevant to this thesis, including chi-squared (χ^2) test, Fisher's exact test, and permutation testing, as well as multiple testing procedures.

3.1 Large Language Models

Large language models (LLMs) are *language models (LMs)* with billions of parameters that have revolutionized natural language processing (**NLP**) through their ability to understand, generate, and reason with natural language text across diverse tasks. The fundamental goal of an **LM** is to use a probability distribution over all possible words within a language to predict the next word token given a preceding context [35]. By learning these statistical patterns in language, **LMs** can be applied to a wide range of **NLP** tasks.

Early approaches to language modeling date back to the 1960s, with attempts to explicitly encode grammatical and syntactic rules of natural language into rule sets and regex patterns [35]. As the full complexity of natural languages could not be summarized into a limited set of rules, these rule-based systems were very domain-specific and limited in their scope [35]. From the 1980s onward, research transitioned toward statistical **LMs**, which relied on data-driven learning rather than manually crafted rules. Among these, *n-gram models* became widely used, leveraging frequency-based co-occurrence statistics to model short-range dependencies in text [35].

In the early 2000s, Bengio et al. introduced the use of *neural networks* for language modeling [36], marking the first application of a feed-forward neural architecture combined with

distributed word representations (*embeddings*) to learn semantic meaning beyond discrete word units [35, 36]. This development laid the foundation for modern language models by demonstrating that words could be represented in a continuous vector space, enabling models to generalize across linguistic patterns more effectively.

Building upon these ideas, *recurrent neural networks (RNNs)* emerged as a natural fit for sequential language data, as their recurrent structure allows information to persist across time steps, making them well-suited for tasks such as language modeling and speech recognition [37, 38]. However, despite their ability to model temporal dependencies, RNNs introduced new challenges, most notably vanishing and exploding gradients during training, which hindered their capacity to learn long-term dependencies, and limited scalability due to their inherently sequential nature [38].

A paradigm shift was triggered by the introduction of the *Transformer* architecture, initially proposed by Vaswani et al. in their famous paper “Attention is all you need” [39]. The core innovation of Transformers is their *self-attention* mechanism, which enables the model to compute contextualized representations of tokens by relating each token in a sequence to all others simultaneously [38, 39]. For each token, the model learns query, key, and value vectors, allowing it to weigh the relevance of surrounding tokens and aggregate their information into a context-aware embedding [39]. Since the architecture lacks an inherent understanding of word order, positional encodings are incorporated to provide information on the sequence token order [38]. Unlike RNNs, self-attention enables Transformers to process token sequences in parallel, significantly improving training efficiency and enabling more effective modeling of long-range relationships between words [38].

The *generative pre-trained transformer (GPT)* series has played a pivotal role in demonstrating the potential of large-scale LLMs, with each iteration showcasing significant improvements in text generation quality, reasoning capabilities, and general performance enhancement across diverse NLP tasks [38]. Multiple masked decoder blocks based on self-attention are stacked to autoregressively predict the next token in a sequence without the need for an encoder component [40]. The initial GPT model (2018), with 117 million parameters, first showcased the potential of pre-training a decoder-only Transformer architecture on a large text corpus [38]. Its successors demonstrated that model performance scales with increased parameter counts: GPT-2 (2019), with 1.5 billion parameters, showed improved text coherence and generation capabilities, while GPT-3 (2020), with 175 billion parameters, achieved breakthrough performance in few-shot learning, enabling the model to perform diverse NLP tasks through prompt examples rather than requiring task-specific fine-tuning [3, 38].

OpenAI applied *reinforcement learning from human feedback (RLHF)* to enhance their models' capabilities to produce natural-sounding responses that align with user instructions, resulting in the releases of InstructGPT and subsequently ChatGPT, which became the first widely accessible LLM designed for conversational interaction and rapidly gained mainstream popularity [41, 42]. Subsequent OpenAI releases, including GPT-4 [43, 44], GPT-4o [45], GPT-4.1 [46] and GPT-4.5 [47], have demonstrated continued improvements in general task performance, featuring longer context windows, enhanced multilingual understanding, better multimodal support, and shorter response times, though OpenAI has not disclosed detailed architectural changes or training methodologies for these newer models except for scaling up unsupervised learning for GPT-4.5 [47].

While OpenAI models are proprietary and cannot be used locally, many open-weight alternatives such as DeepSeek, Gemma, Mistral, and Phi models have been released over the last few years [48, 49]. Among these, the Llama family of models developed by Meta AI has emerged as particularly popular.

The initial LLaMA¹⁰ models, released in early 2023, demonstrated that smaller models with parameter counts ranging from 7 billion to 65 billion parameters could outperform much larger models like GPT-3 (175 billion parameters) on most benchmarks while using only publicly available training data and providing clear documentation of their architectural changes [54].

Llama 2, released in July 2023, extended the model family with versions ranging from 7 billion to 70 billion parameters and introduced Llama 2-Chat models optimized for dialogue through instruction tuning and RLHF [51]. Meanwhile, Llama 3 and 3.1, released in April and July 2024, respectively, significantly scaled up to 405 billion parameters with 15.6 trillion training tokens and enhanced data curation pipelines [52].

The latest Llama 4 series, released in early 2025, represents a major architectural shift by adopting a Mixture of Experts (MoE) design for the first time in the Llama family, where only a subset of parameters is activated per token to improve computational efficiency [53]. The series includes three main variants – Llama 4 Scout, Llama 4 Maverick, and Llama 4 Behemoth – that vary in their purpose with different parameter counts and expert configurations (ranging from 17 billion to 288 billion active parameters and 109 billion to 2 trillion total parameters, with 16 or 128 experts) [53]. The models are claimed to have enhanced multimodal capabilities, industry-leading context window sizes, and significantly improved performance on reasoning and coding benchmarks [53].

A recent development in the field is the emergence of reasoning-oriented LLMs, which aim to improve multi-step logical and mathematical problem solving. Early progress stemmed

¹⁰The naming shifted from the acronym-style *LLaMA* (Large Language Model Meta AI), used for the first generation [50], to the simplified *Llama* capitalization in later model releases [51–53].

from Chain-of-Thought (CoT) prompting, which showed that encouraging models to generate intermediate reasoning steps leads to significantly better performance on complex tasks [55].

Building on this, modern *reasoning models* integrate CoT principles directly into training through reinforcement learning, which enables the automated generation of high-quality reasoning patterns via trial-and-error search algorithms [56]. Reasoning models like OpenAI’s latest GPT-5 model series are trained to “think” before responding by producing internal reasoning tokens that break down problems and consider multiple approaches, followed by generating visible output tokens based on this reasoning process [57].

Despite their impressive capabilities, modern LLMs face several significant limitations and ethical concerns that impact their deployment in real-world applications. Due to their statistical approach to next token prediction based on training data patterns, they can produce factually incorrect or misleading outputs, commonly known as *hallucinations* [58]. The lack of transparency in training data composition further complicates evaluation processes, as it becomes difficult to determine which specific sources were encountered during training. This could result in data contamination where models might appear to perform well on specific tasks due to memorized information rather than genuine understanding [59]. The black-box nature of LLMs also introduces challenges in controlling the generated outputs, making it difficult to enforce specific formatting, structure, or content constraints, even through carefully crafted prompts.

Additionally, inherited biases from training data can reproduce social, cultural, or gender prejudices in generated content [60], and LLM outputs may inadvertently resemble existing content, creating potential intellectual property and copyright violations [61]. To address these challenges, robust governance measures should be implemented when integrating LLMs into real-world applications, including continuous evaluation of model behavior with integrated bias monitoring and human oversight [62, 63].

3.2 Classification

The task of verifying a citation statement by assigning it a label (Substantiated or Unsubstantiated) is a *classification problem*. In the field of machine learning, a classification problem refers to the task of predicting the class label from a finite set Y representing $k = |Y|$ different classes based on feature vectors drawn from a feature space X [64–66]. A *classifier* f is a function $f : X \rightarrow Y$, which, for a labelled dataset $D = \{(x_i, y_i)\}_{i=1}^n$ with $n = |D|$ data objects, assigns a predicted label $\hat{y}_i \in Y$ to a feature vector x_i [64–66]. A prediction \hat{y}_i is considered correct if it matches the target label y_i , otherwise it is

incorrect. Applied to the context of this thesis, the classifier function is the **LLM**, which generates a response containing a target label $\hat{y}_i \in \{\text{Substantiated, Unsubstantiated}\}$ based on the given prompt. The prompt contains the feature values of one data row of the dataset. More specifically, the feature vector x_i consists of the citation statement, the citing paper title, the reference paper title, abstract and reference number, as well as excerpts from the reference paper text are relevant to the citation statement.

3.2.1 Classification Evaluation Metrics

In order to evaluate and compare the performance of different classifiers, several classification metrics can be used. The most relevant ones for the evaluation within this thesis are explained in this section. Which evaluation metrics can be applied depends on the number of different classes k . For $k = 2$, the classification is called *two-class* or *binary* classification, and for $k > 2$, it is called *multiclass* classification. The multiclass classification evaluation metrics are generally extended versions of the binary classification metrics. Therefore, the binary classification evaluation metrics are explained first.

Binary Classification

There are two different classes in a binary classification setting, which are referred to as a *positive* and a *negative* class for the purpose of the evaluation. The class of most interest, which in most cases is the *minority class* (containing fewest samples), is typically defined as the positive class [67]. In the case of citation verification, it is expected that the number of correct citations within scientific publications is higher than the number of erroneous citations. For this reason, and because the focus of this thesis is on detecting citation errors, many of the evaluations of this thesis focus on metrics calculated by defining the Unsubstantiated class as the positive class. Nevertheless, it can make sense to calculate the following metrics from the perspectives of both classes to have the full picture.

The evaluation metrics are calculated based on the *confusion matrix*, which in the case of binary classification is a 2×2 matrix containing the numbers of predictions per class value for each actual (target) class value [64]. In a two-class classification setting, these numbers are called True Positives (TP), False Positives (FP), True Negatives (TN), and False Negatives (FN), as displayed in table 3.1.

One of the most often calculated classification metrics is the *accuracy*, which is the overall number of correct predictions compared to all predictions [64]. In some scenarios, especially within a classifier training process, it might make more sense to calculate the *error rate* instead, which is the percentage of false predictions and therefore the exact opposite

Table 3.1: Schematic illustration of a confusion matrix for binary classification

		PREDICTED	
		Positive	Negative
ACTUAL	Positive	True Positives (TP)	False Negatives (FN)
	Negative	False Positives (FP)	True Negatives (TN)

of the accuracy [65]. Both metrics range from 0 to 1, where classifier performance is better when the accuracy is higher and the error rate is lower. Accuracy and error rate are calculated from the confusion matrix as follows [64]:

$$\text{Accuracy} = \frac{\text{Number of Correct Predictions}}{\text{Total Number of Predictions}} = \frac{TP + TN}{TP + TN + FP + FN} \quad (3.1)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Error Rate} &= \frac{\text{Number of False Predictions}}{\text{Total Number of Predictions}} = \frac{FP + FN}{TP + TN + FP + FN} \quad (3.2) \\ &= 1 - \text{Accuracy} \end{aligned}$$

Accuracy and error rate weigh each prediction equally, which limits their suitability to evaluate imbalanced data. A class distribution is imbalanced when the data is not equally distributed among the classes but one or multiple classes are represented significantly less often than the other class(es) [68]. In these cases, *majority classes* (containing most samples) have a higher weight on accuracy and error rate calculations as they represent a higher proportion of the dataset. The performance on minority classes, which are often the more relevant ones to evaluate, has less effect on the overall accuracy and error rate and might be overlooked [69].

This is why additional metrics, including *precision* and *recall*, should be calculated. Precision is the number of correct positive predictions over all positive predictions, which describes the certainty that a value classified as positive is actually positive [64]. Recall, also called *sensitivity* or *true positive rate (TPR)*, on the other hand, is the number of correct predictions over all actual positive target values, which is the probability that a positive value is recognized as positive [64]. Calculating the *specificity*, also called *true negative rate (TNR)*, is similar to calculating the recall for the negative class as it is the number

of correct predictions over all actual negative target values [64]. The definitions for these three metrics are as follows [64]:

$$\text{Precision} = \frac{\text{Number of Correct Positive Predictions}}{\text{Number of Positive Predictions}} = \frac{TP}{TP + FP} \quad (3.3)$$

$$\text{Recall} = \frac{\text{Number of Correct Positive Predictions}}{\text{Number of Actual Positives}} = \frac{TP}{TP + FN} \quad (3.4)$$

$$\text{Specificity} = \frac{\text{Number of Correct Negative Predictions}}{\text{Number of Actual Negatives}} = \frac{TN}{FP + TN} \quad (3.5)$$

Other metrics that are often used for binary classification are *false positive rate (FPR)* and *false negative rate (FNR)*. However, these are not used within this thesis.

It is important to evaluate precision and recall together, as there exists a natural trade-off between the two [70]. A classifier could trivially achieve perfect recall by classifying all instances as positive, but this would result in low precision since all true negatives would become false positives. On the other hand, high precision could be achieved by classifying only the most unambiguous positive cases as positive, resulting in low recall due to numerous false negatives. While this trade-off is not necessarily monotonic – meaning precision does not always decrease with every increase in recall – it is strongly influenced by both the data distribution and the classifier’s characteristics [70].

The *F1-Score* is an often used evaluation metric that aggregates precision and recall by calculating the harmonic mean between the two [64, 70]:

$$\text{F1-Score} = 2 \cdot \left(\frac{\text{Precision} \cdot \text{Recall}}{\text{Precision} + \text{Recall}} \right) \quad (3.6)$$

Like precision and recall, the F1-Score ranges from 0 to 1, and the goal for choosing and improving a classifier is to achieve high F1-Score values. In contrast to accuracy, the F1-Score is less biased toward the majority class as it takes the class distribution into account by calculating the score from the perspective of the positive class [68]. This is why the F1-Score is especially useful for imbalanced data distributions.

Another metric that is suited for imbalanced data is the *balanced accuracy*. The balanced accuracy is the average of recall values for each class, which means that it essentially averages the probabilities for all classes that a member of this class is classified correctly [69]. For binary classification, this means calculating the average of recall and specificity [69]:

$$\text{Balanced Accuracy} = \frac{\text{Recall} + \text{Specificity}}{2} \quad (3.7)$$

The more balanced a dataset is, the more accuracy and balanced accuracy will converge to the same value [69].

Multiclass classification

Multiclass classification metrics are extended versions of their binary counterparts and can similarly be calculated using a confusion matrix. For k classes, this becomes a $k \times k$ matrix.

There are class-independent metrics like accuracy and error rate which can be calculated over all predictions, and there are class-dependent metrics like precision and recall which are calculated by choosing one class as the positive class and interpreting all other classes as negative classes. This results in true positives TP_i , false positives FP_i , true negatives TN_i , and false negatives FN_i for each class label y_i of the k classes [71]. For a confusion matrix C , where $c_{t,p}$ is the number of predictions for the target class y_t and the predicted class y_p , these numbers are counted as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} TP_i &= c_{i,i} & FP_i &= \sum_{\substack{a=1 \\ a \neq i}}^k c_{a,i} \\ TN_i &= \sum_{\substack{a=1 \\ a \neq i}}^k \sum_{\substack{b=1 \\ b \neq i}}^k c_{a,b} & FN_i &= \sum_{\substack{a=1 \\ a \neq i}}^k c_{i,a} \end{aligned} \quad (3.8)$$

Based on this notation, the *overall accuracy* and *overall error rate* are calculated similarly to their binary classification versions (equations 3.1 and 3.2):

$$\text{Accuracy}_O = \frac{\text{Overall Number of Correct Predictions}}{\text{Total Number of Predictions}} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^k TP_i}{\sum_{a=1}^k \sum_{b=1}^k c_{a,b}} \quad (3.9)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Error Rate}_O &= \frac{\text{Overall Number of False Predictions}}{\text{Total Number of Predictions}} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^k FP_i}{\sum_{a=1}^k \sum_{b=1}^k c_{a,b}} \\ &= 1 - \text{Accuracy}_O \end{aligned} \quad (3.10)$$

All other introduced metrics for binary classification can be calculated per class for multiclass classification using the same equations as introduced before (3.3 - 3.6), but inserting the class-dependent values TP_i , FP_i , TN_i and FN_i instead [71].

Additionally, to assess the overall classification performance, these metrics can be measured over all predictions in two different ways: calculating the *Macro average* or the *Micro average*. The Macro average for a metric is the average over all per-class values of that metric [71]. This means that all classes are treated equally in a Macro average [71]. For a Micro average, the numerators and denominators of the equation are each added up across all classes before dividing [69]. This is why majority classes have a bigger impact on the resulting metric value than minority classes for Micro metrics [71]. The F1-Score is still calculated as the harmonic mean of precision and recall for each average type [69, 71].

The Micro averages for precision, recall, and F1-Score always equal the same value as the overall accuracy, which means that all of these Micro measures share the same advantages and disadvantages. For imbalanced data, the Macro metrics are often better suited because they give equal weights to all classes [69]. The balanced accuracy, which was defined for binary classification in equation 3.7, is the same as the Macro recall in a multiclass classification setting:

$$\text{Balanced Accuracy} = \text{Recall}_M = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^k \frac{TP_i}{TP_i + FN_i}}{k} \quad (3.11)$$

3.2.2 Selective Classification

A variant of a classification problem where only a subset of all data is predicted is called *selective classification*. A *selective classifier* is a function pair (f, g) where $f : X \rightarrow Y$ is a classifier and $g : X \rightarrow \{0, 1\}$ is a selective classifier function that defines which data is labeled by the classifier and which data is abstained from the prediction [72, 73]:

$$(f, g)(x) := \begin{cases} f(x) & \text{if } g(x) = 1, \\ \text{abstain} & \text{if } g(x) = 0. \end{cases} \quad (3.12)$$

Using a selective classifier makes sense when the reliability of classifier predictions is not consistent, which means that the option of abstaining from the prediction is preferable in difficult cases [73].

The performance within a selective classification setting is typically evaluated by calculating the *coverage* and the *selective risk* [72, 73]. The coverage is the dataset proportion of instances where the classifier makes a prediction [73]:

$$\text{Coverage} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n g(x_i)}{n} = \frac{\text{Size of Selected Subset}}{\text{Total Size of Dataset}} \quad (3.13)$$

The *classification risk* is defined based on the *loss function* $l : Y \times Y \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^+$, which maps a class label pair (\hat{y}, y) with a predicted label \hat{y} and a target label y to a numerical loss value, which quantifies the error of the predictions [70]. All classification settings within this thesis are evaluated using a simple 0/1 error, where the prediction is either correct or false:

$$l(\hat{y}_i = f(x_i), y_i) := \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } \hat{y}_i \neq y_i, \\ 0 & \text{if } \hat{y}_i = y_i. \end{cases} \quad (3.14)$$

The risk is the accumulated loss over all predictions divided by the total amount of predicted values [70]. This means that, for a 0/1 error loss function, the risk equals the error rate (as defined in equations 3.2 and 3.10):

$$\text{Risk} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n l(\hat{y}_i, y_i)}{n} \quad (3.15)$$

The selective risk is the risk on the selected subset normalized by the coverage, which is the same as calculating the error rate only on the basis of the non-abstained data [73]:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Selective Risk} &= \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n l(\hat{y}_i, y_i) \cdot g(x_i)}{n \cdot \text{Coverage}} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n l(\hat{y}_i, y_i) \cdot g(x_i)}{\sum_{i=1}^n g(x_i)} \\ &= \frac{\text{Total Amount of False Predictions on Selected Subset}}{\text{Size of Selected Subset}} \end{aligned} \quad (3.16)$$

Other metrics – like accuracy, precision, and recall – can also be calculated on only the selected subset, with selective accuracy being opposite to the selective risk. It is important not to directly compare these results to the metric calculations on the full dataset because the predicted dataset is not the same. If samples that are difficult to predict are left out, it makes sense that the selective performance measures tend to suggest better performance compared to the non-selective classification performance on the full dataset. This means that there exists a trade-off between selective risk (or selective accuracy) and coverage. For different variants of the selective classifier function g , this trade-off can be illustrated using a *risk-coverage curve* [72, 73]. The performance of a selective classifier can be

optimized by either setting a fixed upper bound for the selective risk and aiming for the highest possible coverage, or by setting a fixed lower bound for the coverage and aiming for the lowest possible risk [73].

3.3 Significance Tests

This thesis researches the relationship between different syntactic and semantic features of citation statements and the performance of LLMs on the classification task of verifying these citations. To analyze whether certain identified feature variables have a *significant* impact on the classification performance, statistical *significance tests* are applied. Significance tests are used in the field of statistics to measure whether the evidence from experimental observations is strong enough to reject a previously defined hypothesis about the characteristics of the data [74]. Typically, the tested hypothesis assumes that the experimental test factors have no effect or no relationship, hence it is called the null hypothesis H_0 [75]. The result of the significance test is the so-called *p-value*, which is the probability of observing a result that is at least as extreme as the test statistic from the experiment, under the assumption that the null hypothesis is true. Higher observed deviations from the assumed data distribution based on the null hypothesis lead to smaller *p-values*, as the probability is lower that such extreme deviations could be a coincidence caused by random data sampling [75]. In order to decide whether results are significant or not, a threshold for the *p-value* is defined, called the *significance level* α [76]. The most often referenced significance level is $\alpha = 0.05$, but other levels like 0.01, 0.005, or 0.001 could also be applied depending on the context [74–77].

There are many different types of significance tests with different purposes. Which kind of test to choose depends on data characteristics, the underlying data distribution, and the null hypothesis in question. Within this thesis, the possible association between a categorical variable (annotation attribute) and the classification performance should be evaluated. When the classification performance is measured by a categorical variable (true prediction/false prediction), suitable significance tests are the chi-squared (χ^2) test and Fisher’s exact test [77–79]. On the other hand, when the classification performance is measured through a non-normally distributed continuous variable, which applies to the introduced classification metrics, a permutation test framework can be used instead [80–82]. As there are several different annotation attributes, multiple independent significance tests are performed per type of test, which means that the chance of a significant result in any of the tests increases. This is why the *p-values* should be adjusted using procedures for multiple testing settings, like the Bonferroni method and the Holm method [83–85]. These

three significance testing methods and the two multiple testing procedures are explained in the following sections 3.3.1 through 3.3.4.

3.3.1 Chi-Squared Test

The *chi-squared test* (χ^2) of independence is a significance test used to decide if the distributions of two categorical variables are related or if they are independent [78]. It is calculated based on the *contingency table*, which contains the observed frequencies for each combination of the two categorical variable values (see table 3.2) [78].

Table 3.2: Schematic illustration of a 2×2 contingency table for observed frequencies of two categorical variables (using the values for the annotation attribute *Simple Topical Reference* and the classification correctness as examples)

	True Prediction	False Prediction	Total
No	$O_{1,1}$	$O_{1,2}$	R_1
Yes	$O_{2,1}$	$O_{2,2}$	R_2
Total	C_1	C_2	N

The χ^2 test statistic is calculated based on the observed frequencies O in comparison to the expected frequencies E . As the null hypothesis H_0 assumes that both variables are independent, the expected frequencies can be estimated directly from the contingency table [86]:

$$E_{i,j} = \frac{R_i \cdot C_j}{N} \quad (3.17)$$

Based on table 3.2, the overall probability of a prediction being correct would be $\frac{C_1}{N}$, assuming the two variables are independent. The number of correctly predicted citations that make simple topical references can therefore be estimated by multiplying the number of observed citations of this kind with the overall estimated probability of making a correct prediction.

For an $r \times c$ contingency table, the χ^2 statistic is defined as [78, 86]:

$$\chi^2 = \sum_{i=1}^r \sum_{j=1}^c \frac{(E_{i,j} - O_{i,j})^2}{E_{i,j}} \quad (3.18)$$

High values for the χ^2 statistic mean that the difference between the observed and expected values is relatively large, which indicates that the null hypothesis might be wrong and the variables might not be independent [78]. The χ^2 statistic can be mapped to a p -value by

calculating the degrees of freedom and looking up the corresponding critical χ^2 statistic value for a certain significance level α in a χ^2 table [78, 87]. The *degrees of freedom* df represent the number of values in a calculation that are free to vary, which in the case of χ^2 tests are calculated based on the number of rows and columns of the contingency table [78]:

$$df = (r - 1) \cdot (c - 1) \quad (3.19)$$

For the significance level $p = 0.05$ and $df = 1$ (for a 2×2 contingency table), for example, the critical value for χ^2 is 3.841 [87].

As the χ^2 test uses estimations to calculate the expected outcomes based on the observed data, it is only suitable for larger data samples. An often cited threshold is that for each cell of the contingency table, the expected value should be at least five [77–79].

3.3.2 Fisher's Exact Test

For smaller data samples, the approximation approach of the χ^2 statistic is not very precise [88]. In these cases, the *Fisher's exact test* should be used instead. The Fisher's exact test does not depend on approximations, but instead directly returns an exact p -value without calculating additional test statistics [86, 88]. The null hypothesis of independence is computed by calculating the probabilities of all possible contingency tables that have the same marginal sums (column and row totals) by applying a hypergeometric distribution to the numbers in the contingency table [77, 78]. The p -value is the result of summing the probabilities of all tables that are at most as likely (at least as extreme) as the observed table [81, 89].

Fisher's exact test is usually used for 2×2 contingency tables, even though it also works for larger tables [78, 89], as the computational effort rises drastically with larger tables (more degrees of freedom) and larger sample sizes [78, 89, 90]. Using the notation from table 3.2, the p -value for a 2×2 contingency table is calculated using the following equation [88, 90]:

$$p = \frac{\binom{R_1}{O_{1,1}} \cdot \binom{R_2}{O_{2,1}}}{\binom{N}{C_1}} = \frac{(R_1)! \cdot (R_2)! \cdot (C_1)! \cdot (C_2)!}{O_{1,1}! \cdot O_{1,2}! \cdot O_{2,1}! \cdot O_{2,2}! \cdot N!} \quad (3.20)$$

3.3.3 Permutation Tests

Permutation tests are a general method for determining probability values [80], and they are frequently used as significance tests [80, 82]. A *permutation test* is performed by permuting aspects of the observed data, for example variable values, to receive multiple

equally likely data arrangements [81] and then calculating the test statistic for the permutations. An advantage of permutation tests is that they are not bound to any specific test statistic, but they can be used as a framework on top of existing test statistics [80] to receive more robust and precise results [82].

Closely related to permutation tests are *bootstrap tests* [80, 91]. While for permutation tests, the observed samples are permuted but never replaced, for bootstrap tests, new data samples are drawn from an overall dataset for each iteration, replacing the previously evaluated data samples [80].

This process of repeatedly resampling and replacing from a finite population generates the illusion of an infinite population [80]. Bootstrapping is not well suited for small datasets, as the resulting data samples are small and overlap considerably, leading to less meaningful results [80, 82]. As bootstrap tests replace the data samples, they are mainly used for answering questions about how well a certain data sample distribution represents the underlying population distribution. When testing the independence between variable values of the dataset, permutation tests are better suited than bootstrap tests because permuting the variable values breaks any existing associations between the variables to simulate a null hypothesis of independence, whereas bootstrap resampling preserves the underlying associations by only creating different variable value distributions on the different samples.

There are three variants of permutation tests: exact permutation tests, moment approximation permutation tests, and resampling approximation permutation tests. *Exact permutation tests* enumerate all possible equally likely permuted arrangements of the observed data. Fisher's exact test, described in section 3.3.2, is an exact permutation test [81] because it considers all possible variants of the contingency table with the same marginal sums as the observed table. With increased sample sizes or degrees of freedom, the number of possible arrangements becomes too large to efficiently compute [81]. In these cases, other variants of permutation tests can be applied. *Moment approximation permutation tests* estimate the null distribution of a test statistic by analytically computing its so-called *moments* (for example, mean and variance) and fitting a data distribution that matches these moments [81]. This avoids the need to enumerate or simulate many permutations, making these tests more computationally efficient than exact permutation tests [81]. However, in recent years, moment approximation permutation tests have been more commonly replaced by resampling approximation permutation tests [81]. Instead of calculating all possible permutation arrangements, the *resampling approximation permutation tests* only generate and examine a random subset of all equally likely arrangements of a specified size, a so-called *Monte Carlo subset* [80]. Larger numbers of calculated permutations lead to more precise result values and higher computation costs [80]. This adjustability makes

resampling approximation permutation tests especially flexible for different research purposes [80].

Within this thesis, resampling approximation permutation tests are used to estimate the significance of differences for non-categorical classification performance metrics between citation groups, which are formed based on different values for a certain annotation attribute. The analyzed null hypothesis states that there is no association between the annotation attribute value distribution and the classification performance. The p -value, which is the probability that metric differences at least as extreme as if the null hypothesis were true will occur, is calculated in a permutation test setting by summing all occurrences where the test statistic T_b for the b -th permutation is larger than or equal to the test statistic T_o on the observed data, divided by the number B of permutations [82]:

$$p = \frac{\sum_{b=1}^B I_b(T_o)}{B}, \text{ where } I_b(T_o) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } T_b \geq T_o, \\ 0 & \text{else.} \end{cases} \quad (3.21)$$

3.3.4 Multiple Testing Procedures

When performing and evaluating a significance test, there is always a possibility that the null hypothesis – as the basis of the significance test – is falsely rejected even though it is true, the so-called *type I error* [92]. On the other hand, a *type II error* occurs when the null hypothesis is actually false but is failed to be rejected based on the significance test results [92].

For a single significance test, the *individual error rate* for the type I error equals the significance level α [83]. When performing multiple independent significance tests, the probability of rejecting at least one of the hypotheses when all are true rises with the number of tests performed [83]. For k independent null hypotheses, this *familywise error rate* is $1 - (1 - \alpha)^k$ [83]. This is why *multiple testing procedures* were developed to control the error rate of falsely rejecting null hypotheses over multiple independent significance tests by increasing the individual p -values or decreasing the significance level α (depending on the chosen multiple testing procedure) [83, 84].

A simple and highly applicable multiple testing procedure is the *Bonferroni method* [83, 85]. Applying this method, null hypotheses are only rejected if the p -value of a significance test is smaller than $\frac{\alpha}{k}$ for k independent tests [83]. Alternatively, the p -values can be directly adjusted by multiplying them with k and keeping the significance level α the same [83]. As the p -values of each significance test can be adjusted without taking the other significance tests into consideration, the Bonferroni method is a *single-step procedure* [85].

Although the Bonferroni method is easy to apply in many multiple testing settings, it is not very powerful and should only be applied if the number of significance tests is small because otherwise the proportion of not rejected false hypotheses (type II error rate) can become very high [83, 85].

A more powerful multiple testing procedure is the *Holm method*, also called *sequentially rejective Bonferroni test* [84, 85]. In contrast to the classical Bonferroni method, it is a *stepwise procedure* that takes all significance test results into consideration for accepting or rejecting the underlying null hypotheses [85]. The Holm method sorts all k obtained p -values in ascending order [84]. It then iterates over these values from smallest to largest and compares the p -value in the i -th iteration to $\frac{\alpha}{k-i}$ [84]. This means that the significance level for the smallest p -value is the same as for the Bonferroni method, but for larger p -values the threshold increases. If one of the p -values is larger than the adjusted significance level threshold, the procedure stops and the corresponding null hypothesis and all hypotheses for higher p -values are accepted [84]. All other hypotheses, where the p -values met the adjusted thresholds, are rejected [84]. The Holm method is more powerful than the Bonferroni method because the type I error rate of falsely rejecting at least one true null hypothesis is limited to α for both methods, but the type II error rate of falsely accepting false null hypotheses is the same or lower for the Holm method compared to the Bonferroni method [84].

In addition to the Bonferroni and Holm methods, there exist several other multiple testing procedures that are either more complex or more specific to certain data types or significance test frameworks [83] which are not used within this thesis.

Chapter 4

Methodology

This thesis employs a quantitative empirical research methodology to analyze how linguistic features of citation statements influence citation verification performance in a zero-shot in-context learning classification setting with the purpose of answering the research question introduced in section 1.2.

First, a dataset consisting of citation statement-reference pairs, labeled depending on whether the citation is substantiated by the reference or not, was selected. In order to transform the syntactic and semantic linguistic features of the citation statements into measurable variables, the dataset was enhanced with additional annotations. The annotation scheme was constructed based on assumptions about how certain linguistic features might impact classification performance, drawing on research regarding LLM strengths and weaknesses in other NLP tasks. Section 4.1 explains the process of selecting, modifying and annotating the dataset of this thesis in more detail.

Second, controlled computational experiments were carried out to evaluate the LLM classification performance on the re-annotated dataset. The zero-shot ICL setting provides a consistent, reproducible environment in which the impact of the independent variables – syntactic and semantic attribute values – on the dependent variable – citation classification performance – could be observed. In order to ensure that observed performance differences can be attributed to linguistic features rather than suboptimal experimental settings, two configuration parameter analyses were conducted to systematically optimize the classification pipeline. These are described in section 4.2.

Third, the classification performance is compared across groups of annotation attribute values based on the parameter configuration with the best overall performance. This quantitative analysis is completed by evaluating the significance of the observed differences: Statistical significance tests are applied to determine whether the observations are likely to reflect systematic effects of the linguistic features rather than random variation. Section 4.3 provides details on the methodology of the significance analysis.

4.1 Dataset

This section describes according to which criteria the dataset was chosen and how the data was modified and re-annotated to make the dataset suitable for the experiments of this thesis.

4.1.1 Dataset Selection

Selecting a suitable dataset for the research of this thesis was one of the most important research steps, as the structure and characteristics of the data heavily impact the research results. This is why an extensive literature review on existing datasets for scientific citation analysis was performed as a first step to gain an overview of previous research in the field. The most relevant datasets for this thesis were described in more detail in section 2.4.

A dataset must meet several requirements to be suitable for the research on automated citation verification conducted in this thesis. First and foremost, it must contain a variety of citations from different sources with clear references to the cited reference papers. A direct connection between a citation and its reference papers is necessary to be able to verify the claims from the citation statement against the reference paper text as part of the verification process. Another mandatory piece of information is a classification label that expresses whether the citation contains errors or is fully substantiated by the cited source. Additionally, having some basic information on the citation paper like DOI or title would be helpful because it enables checking the correctness of the citation statement phrasing and adding additional context information to the citation.

The dataset size, meaning the amount of citation statement data entries in the dataset, is also important. In other ML classification settings, the dataset would need to be split into disjoint training, validation and test datasets [93]. The training dataset is typically used to train a classification model, which means that the model parameters are adjusted to enhance the model classification performance on this specific dataset [93]. The validation dataset is then used to compare the performances of multiple models, trained with different hyperparameter settings [93]. Evaluating the trained models on the test dataset should give an estimation on the generalization abilities of the model, which is why the test data should never be included in any step of the training and validation phase [93]. As this thesis applies in-context learning, there are no LLM training or validation phases. Therefore, it would not make sense to split the dataset into multiple subsets, which makes smaller sized datasets viable for this research approach.

Another factor is how balanced the data is between substantiated and erroneous citations. Research by Smith and Cumberledge [2] suggests that the error rate in general science journals is approximately 25%. Therefore, the proportion of unsubstantiated citations in

the dataset used for this thesis should be at least this high, but not exceed the proportion of substantiated citations. Given that error detection is the primary focus of this thesis, a moderate overrepresentation of errors would be preferable to underrepresentation, with emphasis on covering diverse error types.

After initial research and defining the requirements to the dataset, the question arose whether to create a new dataset or to directly use or modify an existing dataset. Both approaches have advantages and disadvantages, but there are a few factors that make it beneficial for this thesis to use an existing dataset as a basis. While creating a new dataset comes with a lot of freedom regarding the data selection and structure of the dataset, creating a dataset from scratch would take a lot of time, which – in the limited time frame of a master’s thesis – would leave less time for performing and evaluating the experiments needed for answering the research questions. Additionally, as there was no direct access to a team of expert annotators as part of this thesis, building a custom dataset would mean that the amount of annotated data would have to be small and the annotation quality would be limited. Another advantage of using an existing dataset is that the research results from the dataset paper could be used for a performance comparison without introducing confounding factors arising from dataset differences.

Two datasets which are related to the task but do not fulfill all of the listed necessary requirements are the *Dr. Inventor* corpus [30, 31] and the *FEVER* dataset [32]. Although the *Dr. Inventor* corpus contains citations which are already annotated regarding their purpose, the corpus does not contain classification labels for the substantiation levels of the citations. The *FEVER* dataset on the other hand does contain labels for verification, but it focuses on the verification of claims which were extracted from Wikipedia and does therefore not contain citations from scientific publications.

The *SciFact* dataset [10] and the *SciClaimHunt* dataset [11] both meet most of the defined requirements as they are relatively large datasets with verifiable claims that directly derive from scientific citations. The only disadvantage, which both datasets share, is that the unsubstantiated claims are artificially crafted from substantiated claims. For *SciFact*, the claims were manually negated by human annotators, while for *SciClaimHunt* four different automated methods were used (described in section 2.4), which allows for an even larger dataset. The issue with artificially crafting citation errors is that this approach might not cover all naturally occurring types of citation errors in scientific literature or it might create a non-realistic error type distribution. Additionally, the paper from Kumar et al. [11] does not provide a link to a downloadable version of the *SciClaimHunt* dataset and the dataset could not be found using search engines.

The most promising dataset found as part of the literature review is the dataset created by Zhang and Abernethy [6], which is a general-domain dataset of statement-reference pairs from journal articles. The important difference to the previously mentioned datasets is that the erroneous citations are not crafted from positive citations, but instead collected from several existing datasets consisting of traceable examples of actual citation errors from published scientific papers [6]. The dataset also contains a lot of additional context information on the citing and reference paper, which makes it possible to manually verify the quality of the citation statements in the dataset and to add further citation annotations. A disadvantage of the dataset created by Zhang and Abernethy is that it is small compared to the other datasets, containing only 250 statement-reference pairs in total, some of which share the same citation statement. Additionally, it is equally balanced between Substantiated and Unsubstantiated data entries and contains a very small number of statements labeled as Partially Substantiated. This distribution does not exactly reflect the natural distribution of citation errors in scientific literature following the results from Smith and Cumberledge [2], but as the dataset is already small and the focus of the thesis is on detecting different types of citation errors, it would not make sense to reduce the amount of Unsubstantiated citations in the dataset to reflect a more natural label distribution. Overall, as this dataset is freely downloadable and fulfills the defined requirements best out of all considered datasets, it was chosen as the base dataset for the research of this thesis.

4.1.2 Dataset Preparation

In order to use the statement-reference pair dataset created by Zhang and Abernethy [6], the first step was to download their annotated data as a spreadsheet in XLSX format from GitHub¹¹. Additionally, it was necessary to download all of the included citation and reference papers to be able to enhance the dataset with further annotations. As manually downloading 178 citation papers and 243 reference papers would take a long time, the process was automated by combining the included paper titles and DOIs to create a reference bibliography¹² which could be imported into *Zotero*¹³. *Zotero* is a free, open source bibliography management tool which includes the feature to automatically retrieve additional metadata or even full texts for the imported reference bibliography. This way, around half of the papers' full texts could be downloaded. The other papers needed to be manually searched by their title or DOI using *Google*¹⁴ or *Google Scholar*¹⁵ and then downloaded through their official publication websites using academic access. Except for four papers,

¹¹<https://github.com/tianmai-zhang/ReferenceErrorDetection>

¹²Using the website: <https://anystyle.io/>

¹³<https://www.zotero.org/>

¹⁴<https://www.google.com/>

¹⁵<https://scholar.google.com/>

all citation and reference papers could be downloaded this way, which is likely due to Zhang and Abernethy choosing articles with easily accessible digital versions for their dataset [6]. In order to connect the data rows from the spreadsheet more easily with the downloaded papers, each paper was given a unique ID, using separate IDs for the citation and reference papers.

After downloading example papers from the dataset and cross-checking them with their data rows, a few problems in regards to the citation statements became clear. One of the identified issues is that if a citation statement had originally contained multiple citations or referenced multiple papers, this information was not included in the dataset. This meant that only the citation number for the reference paper which was analyzed and labeled within that same data row was included in the original dataset statement. There are a small number of cases, where the same citation occurs multiple times in the dataset in combination with different reference papers, but even then only the currently analyzed reference number is included in the data entry. This introduces the problem that it might not be possible for a human reviewer or an LLM to identify which parts of the citation statement should be substantiated by the provided reference paper. The following example citation statement illustrates this issue (citations other than the main citation are grayed out, *Citation ID*: cit046_2):

“Other investigations of Peptide5 in preclinical models have included elucidation of its salutary effects on retinal pigment epithelial cell barrier function [107], diabetic retinopathy [108], and chronic kidney disease [109].”

Within the original dataset created by Zhang and Abernethy [6], the statement only included the reference to paper “[109]”, as this is the reference paper analyzed and labeled within the dataset. With the missing references to papers “[107]” and “[108]” it could seem as if paper “[109]” must contain evidence of salutary effects of Peptide5 on all three mentioned areas and not only about chronic kidney disease. Missing metadata like this, which could lead to confusions for human reviewers, could also affect the LLM classification performance and therefore lead to lower classification accuracies overall. Zhang and Abernethy [6] do not explain why they made the decision to leave out additional citations within the same statement. Within their section about data collection details, they mentioned that even though many statements were taken over from previously annotated datasets, they reviewed each citing paper to locate the statement to which the label was assigned. This suggests that they must have purposefully removed this metadata, possibly to reduce confusion potential for the LLM in regards to which citation the reference paper from the prompt belongs to.

Another modification from Zhang and Abernethy to the citation statements was that there were some statements in the dataset where the beginnings or endings of sentences were cut off or contextual context was missing. In some occasions, this might have the advantage that irrelevant parts for the citation verification were removed, which might be beneficial to the classification results. At the same time, there were some examples where it might not be possible to verify the given statement based on too limited context information. The following citation statement is an example of missing preceding context information, as the grayed out sentence was not part of the original dataset row (*Citation ID*: cit043_2):

“It can be seen from Figure 9 that the presence of these enzymes has no significant effect on the peak current of the sensor. This shows that the sensor has high selectivity for PNK [24].”

As this thesis aims to analyze the capabilities of LLMs in the field of citation verification on a deeper level by taking syntactic or semantic features of citation statements into consideration, it is essential to have complete sentence structures with sufficient context information. This is why all statements in the dataset were manually verified against the downloaded citation papers. Missing citations were added, along with any omitted sentence parts or contextually relevant surrounding sentences necessary for complete understanding of the citation. Additionally, all citations were converted into the IEEE citation style [94] as a consistent citing style might make it easier for the LLM to distinguish between the statement text and the references. In the original dataset, some citations contained numbers and others did not. To maintain the information which reference number the analyzed reference paper corresponds to, a *Reference Number* column was added. As some data rows belong to the same citation paper, in addition to the *Citing Article ID* another column was added called the *Citation ID* which extends the citation paper ID with an identifier. This way it is possible to differentiate whether two rows belonging to the same citation paper cover different citation statements or the same statement with the focus on different references.

Within the original dataset by Zhang and Abernethy [6], three labels are used to represent the level of substantiation of the citation statement by the reference paper: Fully Substantiated, Partially Substantiated, and Unsubstantiated. They included the label Partially Substantiated for cases where there “is a minor error in the statement but the error does not invalidate the purpose of the statement” [6]. Looking at the dataset, examples for these errors are that the statement contains a number which is wrong with the rest of the statement being correct or that a statement is correct under certain conditions with one or multiple conditions from the reference paper not being mentioned. As the analyzed LLMs seemed to have difficulties distinguishing between the labels Fully Substantiated and Partially Substantiated, Zhang and Abernethy merged these two labels to evaluate binary classification

performance which resulted in overall better accuracies [6]. The problem with merging these two labels in the evaluation is that the errors which still exist within the data rows marked as Partially Substantiated are ignored.

For the purpose of the research performed within this thesis, differentiating only between the two labels Substantiated and Unsubstantiated is beneficial for multiple reasons. The first and most straight-forward reason is that within the original dataset, there is a great imbalance within the label distribution as the label Partially Substantiated is used for 14 data rows which make up only around 5% of the data. At the same time, distinguishing between substantial and minor errors introduces a new layer of complexity for the classification task which makes the task more challenging for the LLM [6] but presumably also for the annotators of the dataset. Zhang and Abernethy do not mention how many annotators were included in the annotation process, but if there were multiple, there could have been an inconsistency in regards to deciding between the three labels. Additionally, using only the labels Substantiated and Unsubstantiated makes the results from this thesis more relevant for future real-life applications. For an automated citation verification tool it would be useful to not only detect substantial citation errors but also minor errors like missing conditions or wrong numbers. With this reason in mind, merging the labels Partially Substantiated and Fully Substantiated like Zhang and Abernethy [6] would not make much sense in the research context of this thesis.

The two other options for reducing the dataset to only two labels are removing the data rows labeled as Partially Substantiated or manually relabeling them. With only around 5% of the dataset being affected, removal would be straightforward, but this would completely exclude these minor error types. This is why the 14 data rows were manually re-annotated by examining relevant context from both the citation and reference papers. Any detected citation error, regardless of severity, resulted in the label Unsubstantiated, while citations without any detectable errors received the label Substantiated.

4.1.3 Dataset Annotation

Besides correcting and unifying the citation statements and relabeling the Partially Substantiated data rows, the dataset was further modified by adding annotations to the data. While the original dataset created by Zhang and Abernethy [6] already included a lot of information on the the citation and reference paper like their DOI, title and abstract, there is no classification of the citation statement characteristics aside from whether they are substantiated or not. This is because the research paper from Zhang and Abernethy primarily focuses on the question of how providing LLMs with different amounts of information on the reference paper – only the title vs. title and abstract vs. title, abstract and text excerpts

– affects the classification results [6]. Different from their approach, this thesis focuses on the influence of syntactic and semantic citation statement features on LLM classification performance. Based on literature research on existing citation annotation schemes, summarized in section 2.3, six annotation attributes were identified. Their names, valid attribute values, and definitions are displayed in table 4.1, followed by a detailed explanation of why these attributes were selected, including examples from the dataset.

The dataset was annotated by a single annotator, as multi-annotator validation was not feasible given the resource constraints of this thesis. This approach avoids the need to train additional annotators and helps ensure consistency by eliminating variation introduced through differing interpretations of the annotation attribute definitions. However because the included citation papers span a broad range of specialized domains, comprehensive subject-matter expertise across all areas cannot be assumed. A multi-annotator setup could have highlighted unclear aspects of the annotation scheme and supported its further refinement, potentially improving annotation quality and increasing the scheme’s reusability in future research.

Table 4.1: Overview of the six annotation attributes for capturing syntactic and semantic citation statement features

Attribute Name and Values	Definition
<i>Amount of Citations in Statement</i> $\{ n \in \mathbb{N} \mid n > 0 \}$	Total number of citations within the citation statement; each IEEE style citation “[x, ...]” is counted as a separate citation.
<i>Amount of References for Main Citation</i> $\{ n \in \mathbb{N} \mid n > 0 \}$	Total number of reference numbers within the IEEE style citation that belongs to the <i>main citation</i> (containing the reference number corresponding to the reference paper of that data row)
<i>Amount of Claims to Substantiate</i> $\{ [n_{min}, n_{max}] \mid n_{min}, n_{max} \in \mathbb{N}, n_{min} \leq n_{max} \}$	Interval of possible amounts of claims that should be substantiated by the reference paper as part of the main citation; the exact amount of covered claims (as intended by the citation paper author(s)) should lie within this interval but might be ambiguous from analyzing the provided context of the citation statement.

Attribute Name and Values	Definition
<i>Citation Sentence Structure</i> { <i>Simple, Complex_Single-Clause, Complex_Multiple_Clauses</i> }	Complexity of the sentence structure in relation to the number of relevant clauses for the citation <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Simple</i>: Single sentence with only one clause which contains the citation • <i>Complex_Single-Clause</i>: Multiple connected sentences or compound sentence(s) with multiple clauses where only one clause contains the citation • <i>Complex_Multiple_Clauses</i>: Multiple connected sentences or compound sentence(s) with multiple clauses where multiple clauses contain claims that should be substantiated by the citation
<i>Claim Contains Number or Formula</i> { <i>No, Number, Formula</i> }	Expresses whether the citation statement contains numbers or mathematical/technical formulas that are semantically relevant to the main citation, meaning that they would need to be verified against the reference paper in the classification process
<i>Simple Topical Reference</i> { <i>No, Yes</i> }	If <i>Yes</i> , the purpose of the citation is to mention another paper as an example reference for a certain topic, technical term, or method without including a specific quantitative or qualitative claim about the reference papers' findings.

The annotation attributes were chosen to cover syntactic and semantic features that can be directly extracted from the citation statement without additional context from the citation paper or the reference paper. Syntactic annotation attributes focus only on the sentence structure and grammar, which makes them easier to annotate in comparison to semantic annotation attributes because there is no need to understand the meaning of the sentence in order to perform the annotation.

Amount of Citations in Statement and *Amount of References for Main Citation* are purely syntactic annotations. Since all citations were converted to IEEE style, each pair of square brackets containing numbers is counted for *Amount of Citations in Statement*, while all numbers within the square bracket pair that contains the reference paper number – referred to as the “main citation” – are counted for *Amount of References for Main Citation*. As an example, the following citation statement from the dataset contains four citations and,

as the number of the reference paper is 267, the main citation contains two references – 266 and 267 (citations and references other than the reference paper number of the main citation are grayed out, *Citation ID*: cit065_1):

“In the MDV, 1,000 km to the north and 1.8 km lower in elevation, cyanobacteria inhabit rocky soils [264], lake ice [265], and ice-covered hypersaline lakes [266, 267] in areas that rarely touch the melting point [268].”

The goal of counting the amount of citations and references is to analyze the ability of the classifying LLM to correctly figure out which of the citations contains the reference number provided in the prompt and which parts of the statement are relevant to this citation. This might be more difficult the higher the amount of citations in the statement is, as statements with multiple citations presumably contain more irrelevant information to the main citation than if there is only one citation in the statement. At the same time, higher amounts of references for the same citation might also increase the verification difficulty because the citation paper author could have accumulated information from multiple references. This could lead to more indirect citation statements or make the cited information less obvious to detect within the reference paper. Within the dataset, one citation statement is always verified against exactly one reference paper per data row, which means that in order for the citation statement to be classified as Substantiated, it must be fully substantiated by the provided reference paper, even though there might be other references cited for the same statement. As Zhang and Abernethy do not mention why they removed additional references during their dataset creation, they also do not point out possible classification limitations resulting from this one-to-one mapping. Nevertheless, requiring each reference to substantiate at least part of the citation statement is reasonable because a completely unrelated reference paper would constitute a citation error. Enhancing the dataset to map and verify a citation against multiple references would be interesting for future research, but adding a lot of additional reference papers and verifying all of them against the given citation statements is out of scope for this thesis.

Amount of Claims to Substantiate is a purely semantic annotation attribute, as the meaning of the whole statement must be analyzed to extract the number of claims. Similar to the definition of Wadden et al. for the creation of *SciFact* [10], a claim within the context of this thesis is defined as one atomic statement which is verifiable from a single source. Unlike *SciFact*, the dataset for this thesis contains many citation statements with multiple claims, some of which are relevant to the main citation while others are not. This uncertainty of how many of the statement claims the citation paper author means to substantiate with the reference paper is described by the interval of claim amounts from the annotation attribute *Amount of Claims to Substantiate*. In the following example statement from the

dataset (*Citation ID*: cit108_1), there were three possible claims identified from which any amount from one to three might be meant from the citation paper author to be substantiated by the reference paper (reference number 14):

“In early studies, primary alkyl electrophiles were coupled with alkylmagnesium reagents (Grignard reagents) in the presence of transition-metal catalysts such as copper (Fig. 6A) [13,14].”

The following three sentence parts (*italicized*) were identified as containing distinct claims:

1. In early studies, *primary alkyl electrophiles were coupled with alkylmagnesium reagents (Grignard reagents) ...*
2. ... primary alkyl electrophiles were coupled with ... *in the presence of transition-metal catalysts ...*
3. ... in the presence of *transition-metal catalysts such as copper (Fig. 6A) [13,14].*

The claims were not specifically extracted in the annotation process like in this example, but extracting the identified claims could be useful for further enhancing the dataset as part of future research on this topic. The reason for extracting the interval as described for *Amount of Claims to Substantiate* is that a citation statement where the difference between the minimal and maximal possible amounts of related claims is higher might be more difficult to classify. At the same time, citation statements where the minimal amount of covered claims is at least two could lead to worse classification results because the LLM must verify multiple claims against one reference paper. For these reasons, this annotation attribute is interesting for the research of this thesis. Nevertheless, it is one of the most difficult to annotate because the citation statements are taken out of the context of the citation paper. Further, each author or annotator might have a different opinion on how fine-grained to cite.

There are two annotation attributes which depend on the claims of the citation statement in relation to the syntax of the statement: *Citation Sentence Structure* and *Claim Contains Number or Formula*. For *Citation Sentence Structure*, the citation statement is assigned a label depending on how grammatically complex it is, with focus on the number of sentences or sentence clauses within the statements. The corrected citation statements might consist of multiple sentences, when preceding sentences are necessary to understand the citation sentence or even contain claims that should be substantiated by the main citation. *Citation Sentence Structure* was chosen as an annotation attribute for this dataset because longer or more grammatically complex statements are not only presumably more difficult to understand, but also more challenging to filter for relevant citation statement

parts. This could lead to worse LLM classification results, especially for LLMs that tend to struggle with longer prompts [95], requiring larger context windows and better attention mechanisms. Example sentences for the three labels *Simple*, *Complex_Single-Clause* and *Complex_Multiple_Clauses* for *Citation Sentence Structure* are included in the appendix in section A.1. *Claim Contains Number or Formula* does not focus on sentence grammar but can still be seen as syntax related because the statement is searched for specific text tokens, specifically for numbers or special characters related to technical or mathematical formulas. Statements which are labeled as *Formula* do not necessarily contain a full formula, but could refer to parts of a previously defined formula. They must contain formula-related expressions or special characters though, as demonstrated in the following example from the dataset (*Citation ID*: cit009_1):

“ $\|\theta\|_2^2$ is the regularization term of l_2 parametric, which is used to reduce the parameter space and avoid overfitting [20, 21, 22, 23].”

As shown in this example, a statement labeled as *Formula* can also contain numbers. *Claim Contains Number or Formula* was chosen as an annotation attribute because the performance of LLMs on mathematical reasoning tasks tends to be worse than on purely textual tasks [96], especially when the included numbers are large [97] or the numbers need to be interpreted within a linguistic context [27]. For this reason, the classification performance of an LLM might be worse if a specific number or formula within the citation statement would need to be verified against the reference paper. The definition of *Claim Contains Number or Formula* requires the number or formula to be semantically related to the main citation. This decision was made to leave out citations that include numbers which are completely irrelevant to the main citation because these should have no effect on the classification performance and could distort the overall results for this annotation attribute.

The last annotation attribute, called *Simple Topical Reference*, is purely semantic because it focuses on the purpose of the citation. As discussed in section 2.3, there are many different existing annotation schemes to label citations based on their purpose, most of which are quite fine-grained. As this dataset contains only 250 data rows – substantially smaller than other claim verification datasets – distributing the data across numerous classes would yield very few entries per class. This would diminish the reliability of classification results, as random variations could disproportionately impact the results. This is why *Simple Topical Reference* splits the data into only two groups by focusing on only one aspect of citation purposes. The underlying assumption for this annotation attribute is that citation statements which do not contain substantial claims specific to the findings of the reference paper might be easier to classify. Sometimes, the title or abstract of the reference paper might be enough to verify the citation statement because the reference is only cited as an

example or to refer to a broader topic, as is the case in the following example statement (*Citation ID*: cit001_1):

“Others have aimed to reduce irreversibility or optimize energy-consumed devices [35, 36, 37, 38].”

The results from Zhang and Abernethy state that even when LLMs are only given the titles of reference papers with no further information, the classification accuracy for their overall best performing LLM, GPT-4 Turbo, was still 75.2% compared to 86% for when all information (title, abstract, excerpts) was given [6]. Possible explanations could be that the additional reference paper information may be unnecessary in some cases, or that LLMs verify citation statements at least partially based on parametric knowledge acquired from scientific papers used during their training processes. The annotation attribute *Simple Topical Reference* could provide useful insights into these assumptions.

The distributions of the annotation attribute values are discussed in section 6.1, and the full corrected and re-annotated dataset for this thesis is available for download from GitHub¹⁶.

4.2 Configuration Parameter Analyses

There are various different influence factors that could impact performance on the classification task of citation verification. Although the main research focus of this thesis is to analyze how syntactic and semantic features of citation statements influence the classification performance, it is important that the base implementation of the classification pipeline is robust and uses sensible configuration parameter values in order to generate meaningful results. The implemented classification pipeline for the experiments of this thesis is similar to the architecture described by Zhang and Abernethy, who published LLM classification accuracies for their dataset [6]. It was a logical first step to attempt to reproduce and optimize the classification performance relative to their reported values by using the original dataset and adjusting the configuration parameters of the implemented classification pipeline. In a second analysis, this baseline configuration was further enhanced for the research on the revised and re-annotated dataset of this thesis.

While Zhang and Abernethy give a short overview on their implemented pipeline, they did not publish their source code and do not go into detail on the configuration options that they chose for the integrated tools and libraries. In the process of implementing the classification pipeline for this thesis, inspired by their description, the following configuration parameters were identified:

¹⁶<https://github.com/insabelter/automated-citation-verification>

- GROBID model version (library for PDF text extraction)
- Reference paper text extraction method
- Text splitter for chunking
- Chunk size and token overlap
- Text embedding for indexing
- Prompt wording
- Classifier LLM
- Prompting temperature of the classifier LLM

The only configuration parameters of these for which no different values were tested out within this analysis are the GROBID model version and the prompting temperature. While there is also a lightweight image of GROBID, the full GROBID model was used as it is claimed to provide the best accuracy based on the GROBID documentation [98]. The prompting temperature was always set to 0 to have consistent and reproducible results. The implemented classification pipeline is explained in more detail in chapter 5.

4.2.1 Configuration Optimization on the Original Dataset

The purpose of the first configuration parameter analysis is to reproduce and improve upon the results of Zhang and Abernethy [6]. Therefore, the chunk size for this first analysis was set to 256 with a token overlap of 20 because these are the values they used for their research [6]. Performing a configuration parameter analysis means repeating the whole classification pipeline multiple times, including a lot of LLM prompting. This is why the OpenAI GPT-3.5 Turbo model was used throughout this first analysis. Out of the three models compared by Zhang and Abernethy (GPT-3.5 Turbo, GPT-4 Turbo, GPT-4o) [6], the GPT-3.5 Turbo model was the cheapest and fastest to prompt at the time of research. For this first analysis, the original prompt from Zhang and Abernethy was used to reproduce their three-class classification on the original dataset. The configuration parameters that were tested out in this analysis include the text splitter used for chunking, the text embedding used for indexing, and the reference paper text extraction method.

LlamaIndex, the LLM framework used by Zhang and Abernethy for reference text excerpt retrieval, provides several different text splitters [99]:

- *CodeSplitter*: specifically designed for source code
- *TokenTextSplitter*: splits token-based to match exactly the given chunk size and token overlap
- *SentenceSplitter*: vaguely splits based on chunk size and token overlap while trying to maintain sentence structures

- *SentenceWindowNodeParser*: splits into sentences with sentence overlaps (window size)
- *SemanticSplitterNodeParser*: splits into semantically similar sentences based on embedding similarity

As Zhang and Abernethy published their chunk size and overlap, the only text splitters they could have used are the *TokenTextSplitter* and the *SentenceSplitter*, which is why these two were compared as part of this first analysis. The main configuration, including the text splitter, was not changed for the second analysis because testing out multiple text splitters in combination with further configuration parameters did not fit the time constraints of this thesis. However, other text splitters like the *SentenceWindowNodeParser* and the *SemanticSplitterNodeParser* could be interesting for future research, as they are claimed to better maintain semantic sentence structures [99].

Regarding the text embedding, LlamaIndex supports many different embeddings and even provides a base class for integrating a self-implemented embedding [100]. Their default is *text-embedding-ada-002* from OpenAI [100]. An OpenAI API key was already created for prompting the OpenAI GPT models, so it was logical to compare different OpenAI embeddings within this analysis. OpenAI provides three different text embeddings at the time of writing this thesis, including *text-embedding-ada-002*, *text-embedding-3-small* and *text-embedding-3-large* [101]. The *text-embedding-3-large* is claimed to have the best performance out of them and is the most expensive, while *text-embedding-3-small* is the cheapest one, but is described by OpenAI as still being more performant than their ada embedding models [102–104]. This is why the small and large OpenAI embeddings were chosen for this first configuration parameter analysis.

As the TEI documents, structured XML documents resulting from the GROBID text extraction, contain a lot of metadata other than the pure research paper text, a paper body text extraction (PBTE) component was manually implemented to extract only the scientific text within the main body of the TEI document (explained in more detail in the following implementation chapter 5). The last configuration option that was tested out in this initial analysis was the text extraction method by comparing whether the PBTE component improves the classification performance in comparison to directly chunking the raw text from all XML tags of the TEI document.

A grid search was applied to test these three configuration parameters with two values each, which means that a total of eight iterations of the classification pipeline were performed. For this first parameter analysis, the results were evaluated similarly to the evaluation methods of Zhang and Abernethy to have a meaningful comparison. This means that the overall accuracies were calculated for a three-class setting, and for a two-class setting

by merging the Partially Substantiated and Fully Substantiated predictions [6]. Accuracy alone is generally not a very meaningful metric, especially if the data is imbalanced, which is the case for the original dataset with a clear minority of Partially Substantiated labelled data rows. For this reason, precision, recall and F1-Score per class and balanced accuracy across classes were calculated for both the three-class and the two-class classification. The results of the first configuration parameter analysis are presented in section 6.2.

4.2.2 Configuration Enhancement for the Re-Annotated Dataset

While the first configuration parameter analysis was based on the original dataset, the second analysis was performed after correcting the citation statements and adding annotations, as described in section 4.1.3. During this annotation process, the labeling was adjusted and the previously Partially Substantiated data rows were re-assigned to one of the two labels Substantiated and Unsubstantiated. These changes substantially changed the dataset and the classification prompt in a way that makes it no longer sensible to compare the classification performance to the results from Zhang and Abernethy [6]. Nevertheless, the classification performance could be further improved by evaluating different configuration parameter values that were fixed within the first analysis. This includes comparing the performance of different LLMs and testing out different chunk sizes. As the first analysis did not give a clear answer on the effects of using different reference text extraction methods, the second analysis also included a comparison of applying the PBTE component as opposed to using the raw text from the TEI document XML tags.

The chunk size was set to 256 by Zhang and Abernethy [6], so this value was used within the first analysis. This is a comparatively small chunk size, as LlamaIndex uses a default chunk size of 1,024 for the *TokenTextSplitter* and the *SentenceSplitter* [99]. A reason to use smaller chunk sizes could be that three of the resulting chunks will be included in the classification prompt, which is already long without the excerpts (an example prompt is shown in appendix section B.1). Longer prompts might make it more difficult for the classifying LLM's attention mechanism to extract the most relevant parts of the prompt. Liu et al. [95] demonstrate that LLMs tend to perform worse when they need to retrieve information from long input contexts, especially when the relevant information is in the middle of the prompt. At the same time, larger chunk sizes mean that the classifying LLM is generally provided more information and the chance might be better that the most relevant sentences from the reference paper are fully included in the prompt. This is why a chunk size of 1,024 tokens was compared to 256 tokens in this second configuration parameter analysis. It was considered to use even larger chunk sizes or even provide the whole reference paper texts to the LLM, but due to the OpenAI's limitations of simultaneously

queued tokens for their LLMs leading to a long and inconsistent prompting experience as is, this was not feasible within the constraints of this thesis. The comparison of 256 and 1,024 token chunk sizes should be an indicator for whether it would make sense to test out even larger chunk sizes as part of future research. Different token overlap values were not tested within this thesis. An overlap of 20 tokens, which was the chosen value by Zhang and Abernethy [6], is also the suggested value by LlamaIndex [99], making it a reasonable value for the implementation of this thesis.

Choosing the LLM to be used as the classifier is a decision with a large impact on the resulting classification performance, as Zhang and Abernethy demonstrated within their research on this topic [6]. The variety and amount of different available LLMs increases rapidly at the time of writing this thesis. As the main research and experiments for this thesis were conducted in the first half of 2025, LLMs released after July 2025 were not considered for the comparative analysis.

Several factors were identified that play a role in the decision of which LLMs are best suited for the citation classification task and for the experiment limitations within this thesis, including popularity, financial costs, response times, context window size, implementation effort and documentation. A high popularity has the advantage that there are already several evaluations and implementations of the LLM in different settings, which can positively affect the scope of documentation and lead to decreased implementation efforts. Financial costs are an important factor within the context of a thesis, as well as for a potential integration of the citation verification component into a full application, even though the overall costs vary a lot depending on the concrete circumstances. A university server was freely used as part of this thesis, which meant that open-weight LLMs were deployed with no additional financial costs. The costs for proprietary LLMs were not covered by the university, so they were kept low. Short response times and large context window sizes are especially important for this citation verification task because the prompts include a long task description and several text excerpts from the citation paper and reference paper. In a configuration parameter analysis, where multiple prompting iterations over all 250 data entries are performed, the response times can sum up quickly and token limits of the LLMs need to be considered.

Four different OpenAI GPT models were chosen for the configuration parameter analysis: GPT-3.5 Turbo, GPT-4.1 nano, GPT-4.1 mini and GPT-4.1. Including OpenAI models in the configuration parameter analysis has several advantages. First of all, the OpenAI models are highly popular and therefore frequently applied in other LLM-based text classification or analysis settings [105–107]. As the first configuration parameter analysis (described in section 4.2.1) aimed to reproduce the results from Zhang and Abernethy [6]

by using GPT-3.5 Turbo as the classifier model, it was a sensible choice to reuse the existing code implementation with other OpenAI LLMs. At the time of performing the second configuration parameter analysis, the OpenAI GPT-4.1 models were freshly released and promised to exceed their predecessors – GPT-4 Turbo and GPT-4o – in performance across multiple benchmarks [46]. The GPT-4.1 model series supports very long context windows of up to one million tokens and especially the smaller models, GPT-4.1 mini and GPT-4.1 nano, are claimed to have very short response times [46]. A disadvantage of using the OpenAI models for this thesis are the financial costs, as the LLMs are proprietary and therefore charged per usage. The OpenAI model weights are not freely available, so the models cannot be deployed locally, unlike Llama models, for example. The OpenAI prompting costs are calculated depending on the specific model, the amount of input and output tokens, and on whether the requests are batched. The costs for batched request processing at the time of performing most of the experiments (May to July 2025) are displayed in table 4.2.

Table 4.2: Batch API pricing comparison of GPT-3.5 Turbo, GPT-4.1 nano, GPT-4.1 mini, and GPT-4.1 [108]

Model	Input (per 1M tokens)	Output (per 1M tokens)
GPT-3.5 Turbo	\$0.25	\$0.75
GPT-4.1 nano	\$0.05	\$0.20
GPT-4.1 mini	\$0.20	\$0.80
GPT-4.1	\$1.00	\$4.00

Simultaneously to releasing the GPT-4.1 models, OpenAI also released two other models, o3 and o4-mini [109]. Both models are reasoning models, which means that they produce reasoning tokens in addition to input and output tokens [57]. They mimic a thinking process, which allows the models to better break down tasks and consider different approaches before giving the final answer [57]. This makes reasoning models especially suited for more complex tasks [109]. At the same time, generating additional reasoning tokens leads to longer response times and higher prompting costs, which is why no reasoning models were included in the comparison for this thesis. However, applying reasoning models to the task of citation verification could be a promising topic for future research.

Additionally to the OpenAI models, two Meta Llama models were included in the configuration parameter analysis: Llama 3.1 70B and Llama 4 Scout. The Meta Llama models are open-weight models, meaning that they are openly published (on the platform *Hugging Face*¹⁷), so that they can be directly deployed and applied, using tools like *Ollama*¹⁸.

¹⁷<https://huggingface.co/>

¹⁸<https://github.com/ollama/ollama/tree/main/docs>

As the university server already had *Ollama* installed and different Llama models downloaded, it was logical to compare them against the OpenAI models. While there are many other open-weight LLMs available – like DeepSeek, Gemma, Mistral or Phi [48, 49] – as the first Llama models were already released in the beginning of 2023 [54], they were frequently applied in different use cases [110–112], leading to high popularity. Llama 3.1 70B and Llama 4 Scout, with download sizes of 43 GB and 67 GB respectively, are capable open-weight models that fully utilize the available storage capacity of the university server. The Llama 4 models were especially interesting for the analysis as they were released shortly before performing the experiments for this thesis [53]. They support very large context windows of up to 10 million tokens [53]. With the steadily rising capabilities of newly published LLMs, the Llama 4 Scout model, with 109 billion total and 17 billion active parameters [53], is a promising classifier for the citation classification task of this thesis.

The second configuration parameter analysis, which compared the performance of six different LLMs on the different prompts – resulting from different chunk sizes and text extraction methods – was performed again as a grid search to identify the overall best performance. Due to architectural differences among the compared LLMs, such as varying context window sizes, testing the effects of two different chunk sizes and two reference paper text extraction methods across all models may reveal underlying performance differences between the LLMs.

The re-annotated dataset classification results are evaluated using the same classification metrics as for the first analysis, which was explained in section 4.2.1. As the dataset only has two labels (compared to the three labels of the original dataset), it would be possible to choose one of the two classes as the positive class and perform standard binary classification evaluation this way. Instead, interpreting the two-class setting as a multi-class classification and calculating precision, recall and F1-Score per class has the advantage that the classification performance is quantified independently for each label, which provides a more detailed evaluation. The main focus is on the classification performance for the Unsubstantiated citations because the underlying goal for the citation verification task is to detect citation errors. In a real-life application scenario, it is preferable for a citation verification tool to detect all errors, even if this means incorrectly flagging some correct citations, rather than missing errors and marking false citations as correct. This makes the recall value for the Unsubstantiated citations especially important. At the same time, the user experience with a citation verification tool would suffer a lot if a large portion of the marked errors are false alarms because the user could no longer trust the application and would need to manually re-verify all of the detected errors. This means that a high precision of the Unsubstantiated class is also important. Therefore, the Unsubstantiated

F1-Score as the harmonic mean of precision and recall should be the main focus of the classification evaluation for this specific classification task. The balanced accuracy, being the mean of recalls, is also a suited metric in this scenario, as a low precision for the Unsubstantiated class is statistically coupled to a low recall of the Substantiated class because they are both affected by correct citations being marked as erroneous. For this relatively balanced dataset, the balanced accuracy should be similar to the overall accuracy.

In conclusion, the best configuration from this second configuration parameter analysis on the re-annotated dataset, including the chunk size, the TEI document text extraction method, and most importantly, the LLM, is chosen based on the overall best Unsubstantiated F1-Score and balanced accuracy values. The results of this analysis are discussed in section 6.2. The classification results obtained from the as best identified parameter configuration serve as the foundation for analyzing the significance of dependencies between annotation attribute values and the classification performance, as described in the following section 4.3.

4.3 Significance Analysis

The main research subject of this thesis is to analyze whether there are dependencies between certain syntactic and semantic citation characteristics and the citation verification classification performance when using a zero-shot ICL classification approach. Applying the methodology described in the previous sections 4.1 and 4.2 to manually annotate the dataset, implement a classification pipeline, and optimize this pipeline based on identified configuration parameters led to classification performance results for the full dataset.

Evaluating the same results, the significance analysis described in this section was performed by grouping the dataset entries by their annotation attribute values, which was done for each annotation attribute separately. This way, the classification performance for all citations of one attribute value can be compared to the other attribute values and against the performance on the full dataset. For each group, the same classification metrics as for the configuration analysis were calculated, including accuracy and balanced accuracy as overall metrics and precision, recall and F1-Score as metrics per class. By plotting and analyzing the metric results for each annotation attribute value, noticeable performance differences can be visually identified as potential indicators of dependencies between linguistic citation statement features and classification performance.

The annotation attribute groups are sized differently, which means that metric differences between groups cannot be directly compared. Additionally, the analyzed performance differences between groups could also have occurred by chance, especially when groups are comparatively small. For this reason, significance tests were applied to measure whether

the observed performance differences are statistically significant. The p -values resulting from the significance tests represent the probability of observing performance differences at least as extreme as in the actual results, assuming that classification performance is independent of the grouping – referred to as the null hypothesis of independence H_0 (a more detailed explanation is provided in section 3.3). A typically used significance level for rejecting H_0 is $\alpha = 0.05$ [74–77], so this threshold was used for this thesis.

Choosing suited significance tests not only depends on the null hypothesis that should be evaluated, but also on the characteristics of the statistical variables. For this thesis, the distributions of two variables was compared at a time: an annotation attribute and the classification performance. Some of the annotation attributes are categorical variables with nominal values (for example *Citation Sentence Structure*) and some of the attributes are annotated with discrete numerical values. The issue with the numerical values is that grouping by annotation attribute values results in groups that can be very small and not very representative. As an example, the annotation attribute *Amount of References for Main Citation* is designed to assess whether the increased complexity arising from multiple references for the same citation impacts the classification performance. This complexity stems from potential ambiguity regarding which parts of the citation are substantiated by which references. Although the complexity may increase with a larger number of references, the underlying difficulty is shared across different amounts. Evaluating each amount separately would result in smaller groups, which could potentially lead to individual edge cases overshadowing the overall trend. To mitigate this effect, all dataset entries exceeding a certain number of references are aggregated into a single group, effectively treating the attribute as categorical rather than numerical. This procedure is applied to all inherently numerical annotation attributes so that identical significance tests can be applied across all attributes. This way, the significance test results can be compared between the different annotation attribute types.

The classification performance can be either evaluated as a categorical variable when only differentiating between true and false predictions or as a continuous variable based on classification metrics like balanced accuracy. For these two different variable definitions, different significance tests need to be applied.

Fisher’s exact test, explained in section 3.3.2, is suited to test for independence between two categorical variables. Compared to approximation-based alternatives like the chi-squared (χ^2) test, explained in section 3.3.1, Fisher’s exact test calculates exact p -values. For large datasets or variables with many categories, using the Fisher’s exact test might not be performant. In this case of only 247 total dataset entries (three of the reference papers could not be downloaded, so the corresponding dataset rows were excluded) and only two to three groups per annotation attribute, the calculations were performed almost

instantly, making the Fisher's exact test the best suited significance test when defining the classification performance as a categorical variable.

The impact of an annotation attribute on classification performance might vary between Substantiated and Unsubstantiated citations, which is why Fisher's exact test was performed three times for each annotation attribute: comparing true and false predictions on the total dataset, on the subset of citations labelled as Substantiated, and on the subset of citations labelled as Unsubstantiated.

Interpreting the classification performance as a categorical variable is essentially similar to only evaluating the accuracy of the classification. In order to better take possible label imbalances in the different groups into account, the classification performance was also assessed through continuous metrics like balanced accuracy. Fisher's exact test cannot be applied to non-categorical statistical variables, which is why a different significance test must be applied to assess the variable independence on the basis of these classification metrics. For this specific use case, a permutation test setup was chosen because it does not rely on assumptions about underlying data distributions – such as normal distribution – while offering high flexibility.

The purpose of using a permutation test setting is to test whether the classification performance is independent from the values of a certain annotation attribute by randomly permuting the annotation attribute values in the dataset over multiple iterations. Each time, the classification metric from the observed distribution is compared to the calculated metric on the shuffled distribution. The p -value is derived from counting all occurrences where the permuted distribution is more extreme than the observed distribution, divided by the total amount of permutation iterations. When comparing the classification performance of multiple groups, a *more extreme* distribution can be defined as having a higher variance. The variance measures how spread out the values of the annotation attribute value groups are by calculating the average of the squared differences between the mean and each metric value [113]. The advantage of using variance as the test statistic is that it can be easily calculated for any amount of annotation attribute groups and that the resulting value is always positive.

For each annotation attribute, a permutation test was performed to estimate p -values for a total of eight calculated metrics, consisting of accuracy and balanced accuracy for the full dataset and precision, recall, and F1-Score per classification label. Each permutation test consists of 1,000 permutations of the annotation attribute values. All metrics were calculated from the same permutations. The randomization was seeded to make sure that results of the permutation tests are reproducible.

With the described significance tests, the relations of six different annotation attributes to the classification performance were analyzed. Together, they form a multiple testing setting. In a multiple testing setting of related tests, the p -values should be adjusted to account for the inflation of the family-wise error rate, as further explained in section 3.3.4. With an increasing number of significance tests performed, the probability of obtaining one or more apparently significant p -value purely by chance increases, leading to false rejections of true null hypotheses (type I errors).

A simple but powerful multiple testing procedure that is often applied is the Holm method [84, 85], which was used for the significance tests of this thesis. Applying the Holm method, as explained in section 3.3.4, all p -values resulting from the same significance testing method calculated for the same metric and dataset subset over different annotation attributes were increased accordingly. Afterward, the adjusted p -values were compared to the significance level $\alpha = 0.05$ to identify significant results which statistically indicate a relation between the specific annotation attribute and the measured classification performance. The results of the performed significance analysis are evaluated as part of the results chapter in section 6.3.

Chapter 5

Implementation

This chapter explains the implementation of the experiments for this thesis, including which tools and libraries were used in which configuration and why.

In order to perform the classification of the citation statements from the dataset, there are several different steps needed to transform and process the data. The resulting implementation architecture consists of multiple components which form a dataflow, as displayed in figure 5.1. The general research process of this thesis is similar to the one described by Zhang and Abernethy [6] because they performed citation classification on the same dataset that is also used as the data basis for this thesis, as described in section 4.1. Their focus was on researching the impact of revealing different amounts of information from the reference paper to the LLM within the classification prompt, while this thesis focuses on how differences in the citation statement features might influence the classification performance. While these research question differences impact the context and wording of the classification prompts as well as the evaluation process, the transformation process of the data – especially the extraction of relevant excerpts from the reference paper – is essentially the same. In order to have comparable classification results, the implementation for this thesis is inspired by the architecture and tools mentioned by Zhang and Abernethy: a 3-step RAG pipeline that utilizes GROBID and LlamaIndex for the reference paper text extraction and excerpt retrieval [6]. Zhang and Abernethy do not share any source code from their research, and they also do not give much information on the configuration parameter values they used. Therefore, the codebase for this thesis was built using only the library documentations and code snippets from similar use cases. To find suitable parameter values, an initial configuration parameter analysis was performed, as described in section 4.2.

The hardware that was used to execute all scripts and to locally run and prompt the Llama LLMs is the so-called *BigC* server, a university server from Technical University of Applied Sciences Mannheim. The BigC Ubuntu server has two Intel CPUs with 26 cores each that support Hyper-Threading, 256 GB of RAM and four Nvidia GPUs (two Quadro RTX 8,000 and two NVIDIA TITAN RTX) with a total GPU memory of 144 GB. For the

Figure 5.1: Dataflow of the implemented tool architecture for the classification process (the diagram was generated using diagrams.net)

research of this thesis, *Python*¹⁹ was used as the programming language throughout the codebase because it is a dominant choice for **ML** and **NLP** related tasks [114] and most code examples that were found as part of the literature research are written in Python. In order to maintain a clear code structure and to embed headings, comments, and visualizations directly into the code, most of the source code is written in *Jupyter Notebooks*²⁰. In addition to the task-specific Python libraries explained later in this section, several widely-used cross-domain Python libraries were employed, including:

- *pandas*²¹: for structuring data into dataframes and performing data analysis and manipulation
- *NumPy*²²: for efficient scientific computing with multidimensional arrays
- *matplotlib*²³: for creating static, animated or interactive visualizations like diagrams
- *pickle*²⁴: for serializing and de-serializing Python objects to store and load intermediate results
- *re*²⁵: for pattern-based string searching and text manipulation using regular expressions

The first step in the implemented classification pipeline is to extract the text from the reference papers, which were downloaded as **PDFs** as part of the dataset preparation. *GROBID*(*GeneRation Of Bibliographic Data*)²⁶ is an open source library which can extract and parse specific parts or full texts of scientific publications from raw document formats like **PDF** into structured **TEI** documents [98]. A *TEI document* is a text encoded in Extensible Markup Language (**XML**) according to the Text Encoding Initiative (**TEI**) Guidelines [115]. It uses different **XML** tags to structure the textual content and to enhance it with metadata like annotations or editorial corrections. In order to convert the full texts of the reference papers into **TEI** documents, the **PDFs** were sent separately to a locally running **GROBID** server, which was started via *Docker*²⁷ image using the following command:

```
1 docker run --rm --init --ulimit core=0 -p 8070:8070 grobid/grobid:0.8.2
```

There are two different **GROBID** Docker images available, a full image and a lightweight image, with the full image providing the best accuracy and the lightweight image having a

¹⁹<https://docs.python.org/3/>

²⁰<https://docs.jupyter.org/en/latest/>

²¹<https://pandas.pydata.org/docs/>

²²<https://numpy.org/doc/stable/>

²³<https://matplotlib.org/>

²⁴<https://docs.python.org/3/library/pickle.html>

²⁵<https://docs.python.org/3/library/re.html>

²⁶<https://grobid.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>

²⁷<https://docs.docker.com/>

better runtime performance and being smaller in size, resulting in a lower accuracy. As the used hardware was powerful enough to run the full image and each of the 240 downloaded reference papers only needed to be processed once, the full GROBID image was used for text extraction.

Although the resulting TEI documents could not include any metadata not already present within the PDF documents, they still contained a lot of information on the reference paper, apart from the paper text, which is not needed for the further research process. The classification task is to verify citation statements against reference papers based on title, abstract and excerpts from the paper. Keeping additional information, like information on the authors or the bibliography of the reference paper, might result in less useful reference text excerpts. It could even lead to misconceptions about the contents if the reference paper itself gives no information on a specific topic but it references another paper that covers this topic. If this topic were relevant to the citation statement, the automated chunk detection of LlamaIndex would likely identify the bibliography entry, and the cited paper's title would be included in the classification prompt despite the reference paper itself providing no information on that topic. This is why a component specifically for extracting only the raw text from the body of the reference paper was implemented. The library *lxml*²⁸ was used to parse the XML structure of the TEI document. As the TEI documents generated by GROBID contain all of their main text content within `<div>` tags, all `<div>` tags in between `<body>` tags are located and, using the *lxml* function `itertext()`, the subtrees from these `<div>` tags are iterated to collect the text and concatenate it with spaces. Any content from figures or tables within the reference papers cannot be extracted this way, which might negatively impact the classification results. An example TEI document and the result from the paper body text extraction (PBTE) can be found in appendix section A.2. To test whether this PBTE method improves or worsens the classification results during the configuration parameter analysis, the results are compared against a simple raw text extraction by calling the function `itertext()` on the root of the TEI document to extract all text from all XML tags of the document. Zhang and Abernethy [6] do not mention if and how they extracted the raw text from the TEI documents before the chunking process.

After the reference paper texts are extracted, the next step of the pipeline is to identify the most relevant text sections for verifying the citation statements. For this purpose, LlamaIndex is used. *LlamaIndex*²⁹ is a framework for building LLM agents for different tasks like RAG [116] for which data needs to be indexed, stored, and queried. As a first step, each reference text is tokenized and split into multiple chunks of tokens with a given chunk size (token amount per chunk) and a chunk overlap (amount of overlapping

²⁸<https://lxml.de/>

²⁹<https://docs.llamaindex.ai/en/stable/>

tokens between adjacent chunks). LlamaIndex provides different options for text splitting, including the *TokenTextSplitter* and the *SentenceSplitter*, which were compared as part of the first configuration parameter analysis described in section 4.2.1. Afterward, each chunk is embedded, meaning that it is turned into a numerical representation vector in a high-dimensional space where word similarity should be represented by geometric closeness [38]. LlamaIndex supports multiple embedding models, with the OpenAI embedding *text-embedding-ada-002* configured as the default. In the initial configuration parameter analysis, two additional OpenAI embeddings, *text-embedding-3-small* and *text-embedding-3-large*, were evaluated and compared.

To store the resulting embedded chunks, so called *nodes*, in a structured way for the following retrieval process, they are indexed into a *VectorStoreIndex*. As the process of embedding the data and creating the index store is time and resource intensive, the indices are persisted by saving the storage context and then loading it again for further processing. In order to detect text excerpts which are relevant – meaning semantically similar – to the citation statement, LlamaIndex provides a *VectorIndexRetriever*, which takes an index and an option for how many of the most similar nodes to retrieve as parameters. It then returns to a query that is handed to the `retrieve(query)` method the most similar nodes by performing mathematical operations to calculate the semantic similarity of the query embedding with the embeddings within the index [117]. For this use case, the citation statement used as the query. The texts of the resulting nodes are then added to the dataframe as a list, together with the IDs of the nodes for good traceability.

Afterward, the classification prompts are crafted using the retrieved reference text excerpts. The prompt template was inspired by the prompt template from Zhang and Abernethy [6] but the task explanation was extended to explain the IEEE citation style in combination with the provided reference paper number. Additionally, the label explanations were changed to match the two labels Substantiated and Unsubstantiated (different to the three-class classification from Zhang and Abernethy [6]). A complete example prompt can be found in appendix section B.1.

The classification prompts, which are crafted from the data of one dataset row each, are in the next step given to different LLMs, and the responses are stored for the evaluation process. LLM responses can differ depending on the existing chat context and the LLM temperature. The *temperature* is a hyperparameter that scales the *logits* – the raw output values from the LLM’s final layer – before applying a *softmax function* to transform the scaled logits into a probability distribution with values between 0 and 1 [118]. Higher temperature values produce more uniform probability values for the different possible word tokens. This leads to more variation in the LLM responses [118]. As reproducibility is

an important factor for scientific research, the temperatures for LLM prompting in this thesis are set to 0. Further, a new chat is started for each prompt to clear any chat context. This ensures that the most likely token is consistently selected during answer generation, resulting in deterministic and reproducible responses when prompting the same LLM with identical prompts.

In order to compare the classification results of different recent language models, four non-reasoning LLMs from OpenAI and two Llama LLMs were prompted, as explained in section 4.2. The Llama models could be downloaded and run locally on the BigC university server while the OpenAI models could only be accessed via their public servers by using an OpenAI API key and paying for model access per request tokens. This difference meant that two different implementations were needed for the prompting process.

For prompting the OpenAI LLMs, the goal was to perform all experiments for this thesis while still keeping the costs low. This means that a special focus of the implementation was on making sure that all intermediate results are saved and each prompt was performed exactly once. Another method to reduce costs is to use batch processing, where multiple requests are bundled into a single batch file and submitted to OpenAI servers simultaneously, along with a defined timeframe called *completion window* within which the requests should be completed. Batch processing makes it easier for OpenAI to schedule all incoming requests efficiently, which is why the cost per request token is lower, but it can also lead to longer and more unpredictable wait times for the answer generation [119]. Another problem with batch processing is that OpenAI limits the total amount of request tokens that can be queued at the same time [119]. As the prompts for this thesis are quite long with an average of around 15,000 characters, which translates to around 3,750 tokens [120], and the generated output tokens also count into the total number of queued tokens, the token limits were met multiple times within this research. When the token limit is reached, unfinished batches are cancelled, which could lead to additional costs for the lost intermediate results. This is why the implementation was changed to wait for the completion of one batch before starting the next batch, which added to the already unpredictable response times and made the OpenAI model prompting process time consuming as a whole.

The Llama models could be downloaded and run locally on the BigC university server using *Ollama*³⁰, which is an open source tool to efficiently manage, run, and prompt LLMs locally and offline. Instead of batch processing, each prompt is processed separately. In order to minimize manual monitoring of the prompting process and to continue the scripts even when the VPN connection to the BigC server is lost, the following Linux *nohup* command is used to start the Python script:

³⁰<https://github.com/ollama/ollama/tree/main/docs>

```
1 nohup python prompt_local_model.py > nohup_logs/<logfile_name>.log 2>&1 &
```

Multiple models and configuration variants could be prompted simultaneously by changing the parameters within the Python script and starting these different script instances as separate processes, taking advantage of the multi-core architecture of the BigC server. The progress of the processes could be tracked by logging into local log files. Similarly to the OpenAI models, intermediate results were saved to prevent losing progress, but without a token limit the prompting process of the Llama models was generally more stable even though the total processing time was longer, as detailed in section 6.2.2.

After all of the prompts were processed and the generated LLM answers were saved, the classification labels needed to be extracted from the responses. Although the prompt template defines that the answer should be given in JSON format and should contain the classification label and an explanation, the generated LLM answers did not all match the expected JSON format exactly. OpenAI recently started supporting structured model outputs to enforce a specific response schema [121], but these were not available for all used models at the time of research. This is why a classification label extraction function was manually added into the implemented pipeline using the Python library *json*³¹ to try and decode the LLM response. Sometimes the generated answers contain introduction texts or Markdown fence markers (‘‘ ‘json{. . .} ‘ ‘), which could be removed by extracting the substring between the first and last curly brackets. If the resulting response text was still not in decodable JSON format, the response was first searched for the term *Unsubstantiated* and then for the term *Substantiated* and, if a match was found, the corresponding label was applied.

After extracting the model classification labels, the last step was to evaluate and visualize the results. All evaluation metrics were calculated directly from the created pandas dataframes containing the target and classification labels. For the significance analyses of the relations between the annotation attribute values and the classification performance, the module *scipy.stats* of the library *SciPy*³² was used to perform the Fisher’s exact tests. SciPy is built on NumPy and contains different mathematical algorithms and convenience functions, including statistical functions. The permutation test setup was manually implemented, applying NumPy to perform the random permutations of the annotation attribute values and to calculate the metric variances.

The full implementation source code for this thesis is available on GitHub³³.

³¹<https://docs.python.org/3/library/json.html>

³²<https://docs.scipy.org/doc/scipy/>

³³<https://github.com/insabelter/automated-citation-verification>

Chapter 6

Results

This chapter presents the results from performing the dataset modifications and experiments that were described in chapter 4. First, the characteristics of the re-annotated dataset are discussed in section 6.1 in regards to the different dataset attribute distributions. Afterward, the results of the two configuration parameter analyses for optimizing the classification performance of the implemented classification pipeline are evaluated in section 6.2. Most relevant for answering the research question of this thesis (introduced in section 1.2) are the results of the significance analysis for the different annotation attributes, which are discussed in section 6.3.

6.1 Annotated Dataset Characteristics

This section shows how the relevant attribute values of the re-annotated version of the dataset created by Zhang and Abernethy [6] are distributed and discusses how the results of the further research experiments are affected by these underlying data distributions.

Table 6.1: Overview on the amounts of dataset entries in the full dataset compared to the entries affected by modifications as part of the annotation process of this thesis

	Amount of Dataset Entries
Total	250
Reference Paper Successfully Downloaded	247
Affected by Modifications:	
Extension of Citation Statement	35
Multiple Citations within Statement	54
Multiple References in Main Citation	135

The full dataset consists of 250 entries, with some entries sharing the same citation or reference paper. For the classification pipeline, it is necessary to have a local copy of the reference paper, which could be obtained for 247 of the dataset entries, as shown in table

6.1. The remaining three dataset entries are left out from the following analysis. Table 6.1 also summarizes the amount of dataset rows which were affected by the citation statement refactoring step of the re-annotation process. This included extending the citation statement where relevant information contained in surrounding sentence parts was missing, and converting the citations to IEEE style while including multiple references or citations within the same citation statement – which were cut out by Zhang and Abernethy. While citation statement sentences were extended in approximately one-seventh of the dataset, additional citations other than the main citation were found for more than one-fifth of all citation statements. During the process of converting the citation identifiers used by Zhang and Abernethy (“[citation]”) into actual reference lists in IEEE style, more than half of the conversions resulted in reference lists containing multiple references (for example “[13, 14, 15]”). These high numbers of modified dataset entries indicate that citations with multiple references or citations are not edge cases. Therefore, including this additional information should have a meaningful effect with regard to better reflecting real-life citation examples.

Figure 6.1: Distribution of the citation paper domains for the full dataset

Figure 6.1 illustrates which domains the citation papers can be assigned to. This information is taken from the original dataset by Zhang and Abernethy [6] and was not revised as part of the re-annotation process. A big majority of the dataset consists of citations from papers in natural science domains like chemistry, biology or physics. With fewer examples, the social sciences, including education, management, social science, and economics as part of this dataset are less represented. This is not necessarily an issue because citation

conventions can differ between different scientific fields [122]. The IEEE citation style, for example, is predominantly used in computer science related papers [122]. Having a dataset which mainly focuses on natural science papers could mean that citation styles and other citation conventions do not differ greatly between papers and that the performed conversion to IEEE citation style should not have a substantial impact on the citation meaning in most cases. Representing and comparing different citation styles as part of the same dataset would add another complexity to the classification task, which is not researched as part of this thesis but could be interesting for further research.

Figure 6.2: Comparison of the label distribution between the original dataset and the re-annotated dataset

Another major modification as part of the annotation process of the dataset was the re-labeling of the originally as Partially Substantiated labeled citations. Figure 6.2 compares the label distribution of the dataset before and after the relabeling process. While the original label distribution was imbalanced due to the small amount of Partially Substantiated citations, the re-annotated dataset label distribution is more balanced with Substantiated citations outnumbering Unsubstantiated citations by 17 dataset entries. The previously Partially Substantiated citations were relatively evenly split into Substantiated and Unsubstantiated citations after carefully reviewing the citation statements manually. For most of the citations, there was no explanation given as to why the citation was marked as Partially Substantiated. This means that some errors identified by the original annotators could have potentially been overlooked in the re-annotation process. Additionally, neither the original annotators [6] nor the annotator for this thesis are experts in most of the fields covered by the scientific papers of the dataset.

Chapter 6 Results

Figure 6.3: Value distributions in the re-annotated dataset for the syntactic annotation attributes *Amount of Citations in Statement* and *Amount of References for Main Citation*

The main research focus of this thesis is evaluating potential relations of citation statement features to the classification performance for the ICL classification approach of prompting an LLM. Different syntactic and semantic citation attributes were identified and annotated, as described in section 4.1.3. Figure 6.3 shows the distributions of the two purely syntactic annotation attributes, *Amount of Citations in Statement* and *Amount of References for Main Citation*. The amounts of references for the main citation are a little more spread out than the amounts of citations in the citation statement, but for both attributes, there is a tendency for the count of dataset entries to decrease with larger amounts of citations or references. This is also why the smaller groups corresponding to larger amounts were merged for the significance analysis, as small groups might not provide meaningful results, especially if one of the two classification labels is underrepresented.

Figure 6.4: Value distributions in the re-annotated dataset for the syntactic and semantic annotation attributes *Citation Sentence Structure* and *Claim Contains Number or Formula*

Figure 6.4 illustrates the distributions of the two annotation attributes *Citation Sentence Structure* and *Claim Contains Number or Formula*, which are reliant on the syntax and

the semantics of the citation statements. The dataset is relatively evenly split between the different defined sentence structures, which means that the majority consists of complex citation statement sentence structures, which contain multiple clauses or even multiple full sentences that are closely related to each other.

Numbers or formulas which are directly related to the main citation only make up around one-fifth of the citation statements in the dataset. As only six citations with formulas exist in the dataset, these two groups are also merged for the significance analysis. Although there is still a noticeable distribution imbalance between citations with and without numbers or citations, this marks the annotation attribute as one of the most promising ones. If the significance analysis results would show a negative impact of numbers or formulas on the classification performance, implementing a selective classification approach that sorts out all of these citations would reach a relatively high coverage of almost 85%.

Figure 6.5: Value distributions in the re-annotated dataset for the semantic annotation attributes *Simple Topical Reference* and *Amount of Claims to Substantiate* (only plotting the maximum value of the interval)

The distributions of the last two purely semantic annotation attributes are shown in figure 6.5. For *Simple Topical Reference*, there is a minority of citations which consist of references to other papers without making any specific quantitative or qualitative claims. Covering a little more than one-fourth of the dataset, this minority group is large enough that a meaningful significance evaluation should be possible.

Amount of Claims to Substantiate is the most difficult of the annotation attributes to evaluate because the values were annotated as intervals due to the semantics-based scope for interpretation. As there should always be at least one claim to substantiate, the lower limits of the intervals do not provide much insight in most cases. The goal of this attribute was to annotate the complexity of having multiple claims within the same citation statement that might potentially be covered by the citation or not, depending on the specific citation intentions of the author. This complexity is best represented by the upper limits of the an-

notated intervals for this attribute, which is why those are shown in figure 6.5 and used for the further significance analysis in section 6.3. While most citations are relatively straightforward with a maximum of one or two potentially covered claims, there are also extreme cases like one citation statement with 16 claims. The value 16 results from a long enumeration of technical terms within the citation statement, combined with a large amount of references, making it unclear which subset of the terms is supposed to be supported by the given reference. For *Amount of Claims to Substantiate*, the smaller groups were also merged for further evaluation.

Overall, for all attribute value groups consisting of at least approximately 25 dataset entries, the label distribution of Substantiated and Unsubstantiated citations is relatively evenly split. The most uneven split occurs for the value *Complex_Single-Clause* of the annotation attribute *Citation Sentence Structure*, where around 70% of the 43 citations are labeled as Substantiated. This should be kept in mind for the significance analysis because performance differences between the two target labels might impact the classification metrics when splitting the dataset based on an attribute value distribution. This is one main reason for applying all significance tests to not only the full dataset, but also to the Substantiated and Unsubstantiated citations separately.

6.2 Configuration Parameter Analyses

This section presents and analyzes the results of the two configuration parameter analyses, which were performed within this thesis to optimize the performance of the implemented classification pipeline described in chapter 5.

6.2.1 Configuration Optimization on the Original Dataset

In the first configuration parameter analysis, the goal was to produce comparable results to the research results from Zhang and Abernethy [6] on their original dataset (before the re-annotation process of this thesis). GPT-3.5 Turbo was used as the classifier LLM and the configuration parameters that were tested with a grid search include the text splitter (*TokenTextSplitter* vs. *SentenceSplitter*), the text embedding for indexing (*text-embedding-3-small* vs. *text-embedding-3-large*) and the method of text extraction from the TEI document (text from TEI <body> tags only vs. raw text of full TEI document). Similar to Zhang and Abernethy, the evaluation of the classification performance was performed in two ways: evaluating the overall accuracies and accuracies per class (equal to recall per class) for all three labels (Fully Substantiated, Partially Substantiated, Unsubstantiated), and calculating the same metrics but merging the Fully Substantiated and Partially Sub-

stantiated citations into one class, resulting in a binary classification. As there is a clear minority of Partially Substantiated citations, in addition to overall accuracy, the balanced accuracy (mean of recalls per class) over all classes, and recall, precision and F1-Score per class were calculated. This ensured that the classification performance evaluation method is the same throughout the different experiments of this thesis.

Table 6.2: Overall Accuracies | Balanced Accuracies for the first configuration parameter analysis on the original dataset using GPT-3.5 Turbo (Spl. = Splitter, TTSpl = *TokenTextSplitter*, SSpl = *SentenceSplitter*, Small Emb. = *text-embedding-3-small*, Large Emb. = *text-embedding-3-large*). Best results are underlined.

Text Spl.	PBTE	3 Labels		2 Labels	
		Small Emb.	Large Emb.	Small Emb.	Large Emb.
TTSpl	No	0.541 0.558	0.537 0.513	0.787 0.780	0.816 0.806
	Yes	0.521 0.520	0.516 0.538	0.783 0.772	0.795 0.782
SSpl	No	0.541 0.537	0.570 0.557	0.812 0.804	0.828 0.820
	Yes	0.545 0.518	0.566 0.596	0.803 0.794	0.820 0.810

Table 6.2 shows the overall accuracies and balanced accuracies for the grid search results of this first configuration parameter analysis. The most obvious classification performance difference that can be derived from that table is that the metric values for the three-class evaluation are much lower than for the two-class evaluation – the balanced accuracy is around 25.4% lower on average over all parameter variants. This finding matches the results from Zhang and Abernethy [6] and was their reason to merge the Fully Substantiated and Partially Substantiated citations into one class in the first place [6].

Apart from this big accuracy difference between the evaluation methods, there are smaller but still clearly noticeable differences in classification performance for two of the tested configuration parameters. When comparing the text splitters used for chunking the reference texts, the *SentenceSplitter* consistently achieves better evaluation results across all iterations, with a 2.1% higher balanced accuracy on average compared to the *TokenTextSplitter*. This result is expected since the *SentenceSplitter* preserves natural sentence boundaries, while the *TokenTextSplitter* splits text strictly at the specified token limit, potentially breaking sentences mid-way and thereby removing contextual information from the reference paper needed for successful citation verification.

A similar performance difference can be derived from table 6.2 in regards to the text embedding used for the indexing process as part of retrieving the most relevant reference

paper chunks. Using the larger OpenAI embedding (*text-embedding-3-large*) achieved a 1.7% higher balanced accuracy on average. These results are consistent with the claim of OpenAI that the *text-embedding-3-large* is their most capable embedding model [104].

The third configuration parameter that was tested in this grid search is the TEI document text extraction method. Applying a manually implemented paper body text extraction (PBTE) method that extracts the text only from the <body> tag of the TEI document was compared to extracting all raw text from the document including the bibliography, for example. The results for this parameter are less conclusive than for the other two parameters, as the text extraction method that yields higher overall or balanced accuracy varies across different parameter configurations, with many differences being smaller than 0.5%. On average, the balanced accuracy is around 0.6% higher in this grid search when not using the PBTE method. Nevertheless, the overall best three-class balanced accuracy, 59.6%, results from using the PBTE method and is 3.8% higher than the second best balanced accuracy, 55.8%, where the the PBTE method was not used. However, these results could in part be due to a certain randomness in the LLM responses. As the results for the text extraction method were not conclusive, this parameter was also included in the grid search of the second configuration parameter analysis.

Table 6.3: Overall accuracy and accuracy per class of Zhang and Abernethy for GPT-3.5 Turbo [6] in comparison to the best configuration result for the first configuration parameter analysis of this thesis (US = Unsubstantiated, PS = Partially Substantiated, FS = Fully Substantiated)

Results	Accuracy per Class			Accuracy
	US	PS	FS	Overall
Zhang and Abernethy	0.795	0.571	0.306	0.540
Thesis Results	0.722	0.500	0.443	0.570
Difference	-0.073	-0.071	+0.137	+0.03

Table 6.3 shows the overall and per-class classification accuracies for the best configuration parameters of the first analysis³⁴ in direct comparison to the results from Zhang and Abernethy for the GPT-3.5 model, using their prompt that includes titles, abstracts and excerpts of the reference papers [6]. Although the same tools and libraries were used and the classification pipeline was implemented according to the description from Zhang and Abernethy [6], there are noticeable differences in the accuracy distribution per class. The accuracy of the Fully Substantiated citations is 13.7% higher in this thesis, whereas the

³⁴*SentenceSplitter*, large text embedding, no PBTE

accuracies of the Unsubstantiated and Partially Substantiated citations are both around 7% lower compared to their results [6]. As there is a slight majority of Fully Substantiated citations in the dataset, the overall accuracy of this thesis is 3% higher. With the research focus of this thesis being on detecting reference errors, it would be preferable to achieve similar Unsubstantiated accuracies to the values from Zhang and Abernethy or better. At the same time, it is difficult to identify the reasons for accuracy differences between this thesis and the results from Zhang and Abernethy. The classifier LLM and the prompt are the same between their paper and this thesis and the parameters that were not described by Zhang and Abernethy were evaluated as part of the grid search. There might be additional impact factors that have not been analyzed within this thesis like the model temperature, which was intentionally set to 0 for this thesis to achieve high reproducibility. If Zhang and Abernethy used a model temperature different from 0, this would add a certain level of randomness to their results which could explain the differences.

Table 6.4: Two-class and three-class classification results per label for the best configuration variant of the first parameter analysis on the original dataset using GPT-3.5 Turbo (*SentenceSplitter*, *text-embedding-3-large*, no PBTE)

Classification	Label	Precision	Recall	F1-Score
3 Labels	Unsubstantiated	0.867	0.722	0.788
	Partially Substantiated	0.088	0.500	0.150
	Fully Substantiated	0.740	0.443	0.554
2 Labels	Unsubstantiated	0.867	0.722	0.788
	Partially/Fully Substantiated	0.810	0.912	0.858

A more detailed insight on the per-class classification performance for the overall best configuration parameters from this first analysis is shown in table 6.4. Considering precision and recall separately for each label gives an explanation as to why the overall accuracy for three classes is so much lower than merging the Fully Substantiated and Partially Substantiated citations into one class. The recall of the Fully Substantiated citations, 44.3%, is much smaller than the Unsubstantiated recall of 72.2%. The reason for this low recall seems to be that many Fully Substantiated citations are falsely classified as Partially Substantiated according to the very low Partially Substantiated precision of 8.8% and the high Unsubstantiated precision of 86.7%. This is why merging the Fully Substantiated and Partially Substantiated citations drastically increases the overall accuracy, leading to a combined recall of 91.2%.

This example demonstrates how altering the evaluation method can influence the perception of the underlying results. Although merging two classes in this case seems to improve the classification performance, this does not mean that it semantically makes sense to merge these classes. The label Partially Substantiated was introduced by Zhang and Abernethy to cover edge cases of citation verification where there is a small error which does not invalidate the entire statement [6]. These citations do contain errors though, so if the underlying goal is to evaluate the performance on a citation verification classification task, it might not make sense to ignore these edge cases by evaluating them as Fully Substantiated citations. As the differentiation between three classes with options for overlap is inherently more difficult than the differentiation between two opposite classes, this thesis also chose a binary classification approach. Different to Zhang and Abernethy, the evaluation choice was made to carefully review the Partially Substantiated edge cases and individually sort them into Substantiated and Unsubstantiated citations. This might lead to lower overall accuracies, but it should reflect the real-world variety of citation errors better.

6.2.2 Configuration Enhancement for the Re-Annotated Dataset

In the second configuration parameter analysis, the classification pipeline from the first analysis is applied to the re-annotated dataset of this thesis, which has more complete citation sentences with citations in IEEE notation. It also only contains the two labels Unsubstantiated and Substantiated and is enhanced with additional annotation attributes (that are not included in the classification prompt). For this second analysis, another grid search was performed to compare the classification performance of six different LLMs³⁵ on prompts with reference paper excerpts of two different chunk sizes³⁶. Additionally, the two text extraction methods, using the PBTE component and using the raw text from the TEI document, are compared a second time because the first analysis did not provide conclusive results.

The evaluation for this analysis was performed similarly to the first configuration parameter analysis. Overall accuracy and balanced accuracy are calculated for the full dataset, and recall, precision and F1-Score are calculated per class for a more detailed evaluation. As explained in section 4.2.2, the most important metrics for the classification task of citation verification are the F1-Score for the Unsubstantiated class and the balanced accuracy.

Table 6.5 displays Unsubstantiated F1-Scores and balanced accuracies for the full grid search of this second analysis. Overall, the values for both metrics are relatively close

³⁵GPT-3.5 Turbo, GPT-4.1 nano, GPT-4.1 mini, GPT-4.1, Llama 3.1 70B, Llama 4 Scout

³⁶256 tokens, 1,024 tokens

Table 6.5: Results of the second configuration parameter analysis on the re-annotated dataset comparing six LLMs with two different text extraction methods and two different token chunk sizes. Best results per model are underlined.

Unsubstantiated F1-Scores							
Chunk Size	PBTE	GPT Models				Llama Models	
		3.5 Turbo	4.1 nano	4.1 mini	4.1	3.1 70B	4 Scout
256	No	0.673	<u>0.753</u>	0.811	0.830	0.802	0.778
256	Yes	<u>0.723</u>	0.749	0.795	0.830	0.808	<u>0.791</u>
1,024	No	0.560	0.720	0.811	0.815	0.801	0.235
1,024	Yes	0.525	0.727	<u>0.821</u>	<u>0.842</u>	<u>0.816</u>	0.086

Balanced Accuracies							
Chunk Size	PBTE	GPT Models				Llama Models	
		3.5 Turbo	4.1 nano	4.1 mini	4.1	3.1 70B	4 Scout
256	No	0.734	<u>0.774</u>	0.817	0.844	0.805	0.770
256	Yes	<u>0.764</u>	0.767	0.803	0.844	0.810	<u>0.791</u>
1,024	No	0.682	0.752	0.819	0.831	0.802	0.262
1,024	Yes	0.664	0.759	<u>0.833</u>	<u>0.856</u>	<u>0.819</u>	0.142

together across the grid search, and both metrics share the same parameter configurations per model for achieving the best values. This suggests that the recall values for both labels are somewhat balanced and that the Unsubstantiated precision tends to be similar to the Unsubstantiated recall, meaning that the models generally do not tend to favor one of the two classes at the expense of the other.

Although the evaluation metrics are the same, the results from table 6.5 cannot be directly compared to the results of the first analysis because the underlying dataset and the classification prompt were substantially modified between both experiments. Nevertheless, the second analysis results for the best configuration of the first analysis³⁷ show a general trend that the measured performance on the re-annotated dataset seems to be lower than on the original dataset, indicated by a balanced accuracy difference of 8.6% for the two-class evaluation. This classification performance difference could for example be caused by the

³⁷GPT-3.5 Turbo, 256 token chunk size, no PBTE

re-annotated Partially Substantiated edge cases. Smaller citation errors might be more difficult for the LLM to detect, which could lead to false classifications of Substantiated citations. Another possible explanation for the performance difference could be the inclusion of multiple citations together with the conversion to the IEEE citation style. Identifying the relevant citation from the statement based on a given reference number is an added complexity which might negatively impact the LLM classification performance. As these decisions for the dataset annotation were made with the intention to better reflect real-life examples of citations, the results of this second analysis should be better suited to evaluate the potential of LLMs to be integrated into automated citation verification applications.

Regarding the overall grid search results, one detail that immediately stands out when looking at table 6.5 is the bad performance of the Llama 4 Scout model for a chunk size of 1,024 tokens with balanced accuracies of 26.2% for not using the PBTE component and 14.2% for using the PBTE. The bad metric scores mainly come from the model not generating valid answers that match the requested JSON format and contain a classification label. An example for such an ill-structured Llama 4 Scout response is given in appendix section B.2.5. It seems that the Llama 4 Scout model struggles with using its attention mechanism to filter out the instruction from longer prompts because the performance drops so drastically from using 256 token chunks to using 1,024 token chunks.

When comparing the chunk sizes of 256 and 1,024 tokens for the other five models, the findings are inconsistent. On average, over all models (except Llama 4 Scout), the balanced accuracy for the larger chunk size is 1.5% lower and the Unsubstantiated F1-Score is even lower with a difference of 3.4%. However, the best metric values from the three overall best performing models (GPT-4.1, GPT-4.1 mini, Llama 3.1 70B) were all achieved using 1,024 token chunks. This could indicate a relation between the model size and the ability to successfully extract relevant information from larger prompts. The Llama 4 Scout model is an outlier for this assumption as it consists of 109 billion parameters [123] and Llama 3.1 70B of only of 70.6 billion parameters [124]. Different to the Llama 3.1 70B model though, the Llama 4 Scout model contains active and non-active parameters with only 17 billion of the 109 billion parameters being active, which might be a reason for the bad adaptation to longer prompts observed in this thesis.

LLM response examples of correct and incorrect classifications from the best performing GPT-4.1 model are provided in appendix section B.2.

Regarding the different text extraction methods, the results are mixed. Over all models (except for Llama 4 Scout), both the balanced accuracies and the Unsubstantiated F1-Scores are on average 0.6% higher when using the manually implemented PBTE. Although the difference is not very substantial, this is the opposite effect compared to the first configu-

ration parameter analysis. Several factors may explain why the **PBTE** component does not consistently improve classification performance. First, for correctly classified citations, the relevant text excerpts may be relatively easy to identify based on high semantic similarity to the citation statement in the word embedding space. In such cases, the presence of additional irrelevant text sections from the raw **TEI** document text extraction may not significantly impact retrieval quality, as the relevant excerpts would still receive the highest similarity scores. Second, the reference paper excerpts may have limited influence on the **LLM**'s classification decisions overall. Instead, the model may rely primarily on the reference paper title or its own parametric knowledge about the relevant topics when generating labels. This theory is supported by the research of Zhang and Abernethy, where the two-class accuracy for **GPT-3.5 Turbo** was only 3.6% lower when not including any additional information about the reference paper in the prompt except for the title [6].

Figure 6.6: Comparison of Unsubstantiated F1-Scores and balanced accuracies for the best parameter configuration of each model

The impact of choosing different classifier **LLMs** is larger than the classification performance differences related to varying chunk sizes and text extraction methods. Between the best configuration of the worst performing **LLM** (**GPT-3.5 Turbo**) and the best configuration of the best performing **LLM** (**GPT-4.1**), there is a difference of 9.2% for the balanced accuracy and 11.9% for the Unsubstantiated F1-Score. Figure 6.6 illustrates the differences in metric values between the models, based on the best configuration for each model (underlined values from table 6.5). The **GPT-4.1** model is the best performing

model among the tested OpenAI models, consistent with the differing model capabilities claimed by OpenAI [46]. Surprising is that the Llama 3.1 70B model consistently performed better than the later released Llama 4 Scout model, even for the smaller chunk sizes where Llama 4 Scout performed just slightly worse. This could be related to the different architectures of the two models, with Llama 4 Scout having active and non-active parameters, which could also be a reason for the shorter response generation times of the Llama 4 Scout model.

Classifying the almost 250 citations of the re-annotated dataset took between 5h0min and 6h45min for the Llama 4 Scout model and around 7h45min for the Llama 3.1 70B model. These times are calculated based on the log files when running multiple classification iterations simultaneously on the BigC university server using nohup (for more details see chapter 5). Overall, the response generation using the OpenAI Batch API was much quicker compared to the local prompting, as most of the models (GPT-3.5 Turbo, GPT-4.1 mini, GPT-4.1 nano) took between 15 and 35 minutes to iteratively complete all batches of one classification iteration of the re-annotated dataset. However, there were multiple interruptions due to failed batches because of the queued token limits of the OpenAI API. These occurred most often for the GPT-4.1 model, which also had the longest response times. Without failed attempts, one iteration of the GPT-4.1 model classification in multiple batches took up to two hours.

Next to the response times, an additional cost factor for the LLM usages were the financial costs. In total, using the OpenAI API to embed the reference texts and generate batched responses for the GPT models cost around €25. Prompting the Llama models did not contribute to the financial costs because the BigC university server could be used for free for these research purposes. Nevertheless, setting up and maintaining a server infrastructure for running LLMs locally generally incurs financial costs, including hardware acquisition, electricity consumption, and ongoing maintenance.

Apart from the overall metrics and the cost factors, there are also differences between the best performing OpenAI GPT and Meta Llama models (GPT-4.1 and Llama 3.1 70B) when comparing the per-class recall and precision. Figure 6.7 shows all calculated metric values for the best configuration of each of these two models. Both the GPT-4.1 model and the Llama 3.1 70B model have a noticeable recall difference between the Substantiated and the Unsubstantiated class, but in favor of different classes. While the recall for the Substantiated class is higher than the Unsubstantiated recall for the GPT-4.1 model, it is the other way around for the Llama 3.1 70B model. Although figure 6.7 only includes these two models, the same general trend can be observed for all OpenAI GPT models in comparison to the Meta Llama models included in this analysis, as shown in table 6.6. This difference in recall values suggests that the OpenAI GPT models tend to generally

Chapter 6 Results

Figure 6.7: Detailed classification performance metrics comparison between the best performing OpenAI GPT model (GPT-4.1) and Meta Llama model (Llama 3.1 70B)

classify more citations as Substantiated, while the Llama models classify more citations as Unsubstantiated. The Unsubstantiated recall is one of the most important metrics for this classification task because the citation verifier should be able to detect as many errors as possible. Nevertheless, the low Unsubstantiated precision of the Llama 3.1 70B model and the overall big differences in recall and precision values for this model mark it as less stable than the GPT-4.1 model in its classification performance. Therefore, the GPT-4.1 model is used for the significance analysis, evaluated in section 6.3, with prompts including reference paper excerpts of 1,024 tokens extracted using the PBTE method.

Table 6.6: Detailed classification performance metrics for the second configuration parameter analysis on the re-annotated dataset across all models (best configuration each)

Model	Overall		Substantiated		Unsubstantiated	
	Accuracy	Bal. Accuracy	Precision	Recall	Precision	Recall
GPT-3.5 Turbo	0.773	0.764	0.738	0.894	0.839	0.635
GPT-4.1 nano	0.777	0.774	0.777	0.818	0.778	0.730
GPT-4.1 mini	0.834	0.833	0.842	0.848	0.825	0.817
GPT-4.1	0.858	0.856	0.844	0.902	0.877	0.809
Llama 3.1 70B	0.806	0.810	0.875	0.742	0.748	0.878
Llama 4 Scout	0.785	0.791	0.862	0.712	0.725	0.870

6.3 Significance Analysis

This section evaluates the results of the significance analysis aiming to identify significant relations between the annotated linguistic citation statement attributes and the citation verification performance in a zero-shot ICL classification setting. The best results of the second configuration parameter analysis performed on the re-annotated dataset³⁸ were used for this analysis. The citations were grouped by attribute value for each of the annotation attributes, merging small groups to form larger groups for the analysis to produce more meaningful results.

Afterward, the same evaluation metrics that were used for the overall evaluation were calculated for each of the resulting attribute value groups. This includes accuracy and balanced accuracy for the full group, and precision, recall and F1-Score for each of the two label subsets. As in the previous evaluations, the evaluation focus is on the balanced accuracy and the F1-Scores, which are plotted for every value group of each annotation attribute in figure 6.8. The plots also include the differences to the evaluated metrics on the full dataset. The advantage of this visualization is that it clearly shows classification performance differences between the value groups, as well as differences between the performances on the Substantiated and Unsubstantiated citations within the same group. A disadvantage is that the groups vary in size (as shown in the x-axis labels), which means the differences cannot be compared straightforwardly since they are inherently related to the group sizes.

In order to evaluate which differences between groups are statistically significant, two significance tests were carried out. The Fisher's exact test is applied to calculate an exact p -value from the contingency tables, which contain the true and false predictions per value group for each annotation attribute. The test was applied three times each: on the total dataset, on the subset of Substantiated citations and on the subset of Unsubstantiated citations. Although this test calculates exact p -values by applying a hypergeometric distribution, it can only be applied to contingency tables containing data amounts and not to evaluate the significance of continuous classification metrics. This is why a permutation test setup was additionally applied. It estimates p -values by randomly permuting attribute values 1,000 times for each annotation attribute and calculating how often the variance between group metrics in the permuted data equals or exceeds the variance observed in the actual annotation attribute distribution. Due to the multiple testing setting, all p -values were adjusted using the Holm procedure.

³⁸GPT-4.1 as classifier model, text extraction with PBTE, *SentenceSplitter*, *text-embedding-3-large*, 1,024 token chunk size

Figure 6.8: Overview of the classification performance for each value group of each annotation attribute, calculated from the overall best classification configuration (GPT-4.1 model, with PBTE, SentenceSplitter, text-embedding-3-large, 1,024 token chunk size). The bars contain the differences to the metric values on the full dataset (balanced accuracy: 85.6%, Substantiated F1-Score: 84.2%, Unsubstantiated F1-Score: 87.2%)

Table 6.7: Fisher’s Exact Test p -values (Original | Holm-adjusted) for the different dataset label subsets (Amt. = Amount of, Substant. = Substantiated, Unsubstant. = Unsubstantiated). None of the adjusted p -values are significant at the significance level $\alpha = 0.05$.

	Total	Substant.	Unsubstant.
Amt. References for Main Citation	0.145 0.872	0.776 1.000	0.156 0.935
Citation Sentence Structure	1.000 1.000	1.000 1.000	0.415 1.000
Amt. Claims to Substantiate (Max.)	0.362 1.000	0.776 1.000	0.236 1.000
Simple Topical Reference	0.313 1.000	0.217 1.000	0.777 0.777
Amt. Citations in Statement	1.000 1.000	0.550 1.000	0.240 0.958
Claim Contains Number or Formula	0.159 0.795	0.029 0.176	0.560 1.000

Table 6.8: Permutation Test p -values (Original | Holm-adjusted) for the metrics Balanced Accuracy and F1-Score (Amt. = Amount of, Substant. = Substantiated, Unsubstant. = Unsubstantiated). None of the adjusted p -values are significant at the significance level $\alpha = 0.05$.

	Bal. Accuracy		F1-Score	
	Total		Substant.	Unsubstant.
Amt. References for Main Citation	0.172 1.000		0.115 0.575	0.241 0.964
Citation Sentence Structure	0.635 1.000		0.447 0.447	0.110 0.550
Amt. Claims to Substantiate (Max.)	0.418 1.000		0.179 0.716	0.673 1.000
Simple Topical Reference	0.539 1.000		0.103 0.618	0.954 0.954
Amt. Citations in Statement	0.266 1.000		0.195 0.390	0.012 0.072
Claim Contains Number or Formula	0.651 0.651		0.185 0.555	0.499 1.000

The p -values resulting from Fisher’s exact test are displayed in table 6.7 and the permutation test results for the balanced accuracies and F1-Scores are shown in table 6.8. Both tables include the p -values before and after the Holm procedure adjustments. In the remainder of this section, the results from figure 6.8, table 6.7 and table 6.8 are evaluated for each of the annotation attributes separately.

Amount of References for Main Citation For the annotation attribute *Amount of References for Main Citation*, there is a small performance difference along all plotted classification metrics from figure 6.8. Citation statements with only one reference as part of the main citation performed around 3% worse compared to the full dataset while statements

with more than one reference performed around 3% better along all three considered metrics. This result is opposite to the initial assumption that citation statements with fewer references might be easier to classify because there is no uncertainty regarding which reference paper should substantiate which part of the citation. A possible interpretation is that citations with multiple references might be more likely to describe established facts in the field that are not specific to a single paper and therefore possibly easier to detect within the reference paper and less complex to verify. Based on the p -values from the significance tests, the metric variances between the two groups are not statistically significant, which means that there is no strong indication for either of the assumed relationships on the basis of the analyzed dataset.

Citation Sentence Structure Regarding the sentence structure and complexity, there is a difference between the performance variances of the Unsubstantiated citations and the Substantiated citations. While the Substantiated F1-Scores are slightly higher for the more complex sentence structures, the Unsubstantiated F1-Scores are noticeably lower for these citations with a difference of 9.9% between the the evaluation on the full dataset and the group of complex sentence structures where the citation belongs to a single clause of the sentence (*Complex_Single-Clause*). The results for the Unsubstantiated citation subset align with the assumption that citation errors may be more challenging to detect when embedded within complex sentence structures containing multiple semantically connected clauses or sentences. Nevertheless, the particularly pronounced difference in Unsubstantiated F1-Scores for *Complex_Single-Clause* may also reflect the unbalanced label distribution within this attribute value, where only 18 of 61 citations (approximately 30%) are Unsubstantiated. Given that the adjusted Fisher’s exact test p -values for this annotation attribute all equal 1.000 and the permutation tests similarly yielded high p -values, the observed performance variations may be attributable to random chance rather than systematic effects.

Amount of Claims to Substantiate One of the annotation attributes where the performance results generally match the initial assumption is *Amount of Claims to Substantiate*. When splitting the data into citation statements with a maximum of one claim that needs to be verified and statements with (potentially) multiple claims, the balanced accuracy and F1-Scores are larger for the group of single claim citations. While these results could be coincidental, it could also be an indicator that citations might be more difficult to verify with higher amounts of claims that are covered by the citation – either in general or specifically for when the verification is performed using an LLM. The consistently high Fisher’s exact test p -values and Holm-adjusted permutation test p -values suggest that the observed

variances are not statistically significant, so the null hypothesis of independence cannot be rejected on the basis of this dataset.

Simple Topical Reference Similar to *Amount of Claims to Substantiate*, the results for *Simple Topical Reference* match the original expectation that citation statements without any claims specific to the reference paper might be easier to classify because the classifier should only need to check whether the reference paper broadly covers the topic that is mentioned in the citation statement. Indeed, all of the metric values for the simple topical references are higher, but the increases for the balanced accuracy (1.8%) and the Unsubstantiated F1-Score (0.3%) are quite small. For the subset of Substantiated citations, there is a more meaningful performance increase of a 5.3% higher F1-Score compared to the metric value on the full dataset which leads to the second smallest unadjusted permutation test p -value of 0.103. The Holm-adjusted value of 0.618 is much higher than the significance level $\alpha = 0.05$, marking these results as also not statistically significant.

Amount of Citations in Statement The only annotation attribute where the significance test analysis resulted in an adjusted p -value that almost met the defined significance level $\alpha = 0.05$ is *Amount of Citations in Statement*. The permutation test p -values for the Unsubstantiated F1-Score of this metric are the lowest of all calculated p -values for this thesis with an unadjusted value of 0.012 and an Holm-adjusted value of 0.072. This observation is also evident in figure 6.8: The 14.6% difference between the Unsubstantiated F1-Score of the full dataset and the annotation attribute value group of citation statements containing at least two separate citations represents the largest performance difference observed across all annotation attributes. Interestingly, the Substantiated F1-Score is 4.6% higher on the same data subset compared to the full dataset evaluation.

The initial assumption for this annotation attribute was that it could be difficult for an LLM to identify the relevant sentence parts for the verification when the citation statement contains multiple citations. The Substantiated F1-Score results indicate that this might not be the case. The LLM does not seem to try to verify parts of the other citations within the sentence, otherwise there should be a performance drop for the Substantiated citations as well. A possible explanation for the large metric difference for the Unsubstantiated F1-Score could be that prompts for the Unsubstantiated citations are likely to contain reference paper excerpts that are unrelated to the main citation and therefore are potentially very general statements that could be applied to multiple contexts, including the other citations within the statement. As the reference paper excerpt extraction is based on word embedding similarity, it could even be the case that the extracted excerpts explicitly cover topics from other citations within the statement, especially when those citations make up

a large portion of the full statement. This is more likely to happen for Unsubstantiated citations, were the reference paper might not include any information relevant to the main citation.

Claim Contains Number or Formula For the annotation attribute *Claim Contains Number or Formula*, there is a noticeable difference for all performance metrics between citations with and without a number or formula relevant to the main citation. All visualized metrics in figure 6.8 are around 8% lower for the attribute value *Number/Formula* compared to the overall metrics calculated on the full dataset. These results match the expectation that numbers or formulas might be difficult for an LLM to verify because mathematical understanding is a known limitation of non-reasoning LLMs [96], especially when numbers or formulas are embedded within a linguistic context [27]. Although this is the highest performance drop that is consistent through all metrics, according to the significance test results these values are also not significant. With an unadjusted value of 0.029 and an adjusted value of 0.176 for the Substantiated subset of this annotation attribute grouping, the p -values are the lowest out of all Fisher's exact test results, as shown in table 6.7.

For this annotation attribute, it could potentially make sense to apply a selective classification approach by filtering out all citation statements that contain numbers or formulas before the actual classification process. With 40 citation statements, this data subset is the smallest of all annotation attribute value groups which means that the selective classification coverage would be relatively high with around 84%. Based on the results on this dataset, the accuracy could be improved by around 1.5% using this selective classification approach, but the resulting selective risk of 13% would mean that around every eighth citation statement would be falsely classified. This error rate would presumably be too high to integrate the pipeline established in this thesis into an automated citation verification application for real-world usage, as regular occurrences of classification mistakes would highly reduce the trustworthiness of such an application.

In conclusion, as none of the Holm-adjusted p -values from the significance tests meet the defined significance level $\alpha = 0.05$, none of the null hypotheses of independence can be rejected on the basis of the significance analysis results from this dataset in combination with the chosen classification pipeline configurations. This means that there are no strong indications for any of the initial assumptions on the annotation attribute influences stated as part of the annotation scheme introduction in section 4.1.3.

Chapter 7

Discussion

This chapter examines the results presented in chapter 6 to answer the research question of this thesis. Furthermore, it identifies limitations inherent in the applied research methodology and explores opportunities for future research in the field of automated citation verification.

As introduced in section 1.2, this thesis aims to answer the following research question:

How do syntactic and semantic features of citation statements influence the citation verification performance of a large language model in a zero-shot in-context learning classification setting?

For this research purpose, multiple assumptions on the impacts of different identified linguistic citation statement features were defined as part of the annotation scheme creation in section 4.1.3. These expected relationships between linguistic features and classification performance were individually analyzed by applying multiple significance tests to verify the statistical significance of the measured performance variances between subsets of citation statements that were grouped by their annotation attribute values. As reported in section 6.3, none of the adjusted p -values reached the defined significance level $\alpha = 0.05$, indicating that none of the null hypotheses can be rejected based on the observed classification results. However, it is crucial to note that the absence of statistical significance does not automatically confirm the null hypothesis of independence. In context of the research question, it cannot be directly concluded from the findings that linguistic citation statement features have no influence on classification performance in a zero-shot ICL setting.

While the results lack statistical significance under the chosen significance testing framework, notable performance variances were observed across various annotation categories. Most prominently, there is a consistent performance decline of around 8% across all evaluated metrics for citations containing numbers or formulas. Although these patterns could be coincidental, there are possible explanations for why the chosen statistical test framework might fail to detect existing relationships within the data.

First, the simultaneous analysis of six annotation attributes led to a large number of significance tests, resulting in overall high adjusted p -values. While the Holm correction is less

conservative than the Bonferroni correction, the complex comparison setup together with the chosen multiple testing procedure may still have been too strict to detect meaningful performance differences.

Second, the introduced annotation scheme may not fully capture the underlying linguistic relationships that influence LLM performance. Additional linguistic factors or complex interdependencies between annotation attributes might exist that could not be detected by the current framework. Furthermore, relying on a single annotator may have introduced inconsistencies into the dataset, as annotation decisions for subjective linguistic features – such as determining the appropriate number of claims that should be substantiated by a citation – can vary considerably between individuals. Future research would benefit from an annotation process involving multiple independent expert annotators following clearly defined annotation guidelines.

Third, the dataset size may be insufficient to achieve statistical validation for the observed performance differences. Larger datasets would potentially yield more significant results, as substantial performance drops would be less likely to occur by chance, therefore similar percentage metric differences to this dataset would result in smaller p -values. However, expanding the dataset or re-annotating another dataset would require considerable additional annotation effort and manual verification, as no larger datasets containing verified citation errors from scientific literature were found as part of the research process of this thesis.

Beyond the statistical analysis limitations, there are additional aspects regarding dataset creation and annotation methodology that should be considered for future research on automated citation verification. The used dataset created by Zhang and Abernethy [6] consisted of a hand-picked selection of citations from different papers of different scientific domains. While this approach has the advantage of capturing diverse domain-specific citing conventions, the present research would have benefited from focusing on a single scientific domain to control for potential confounding variables. However, given the limited dataset size and the relatively even distribution across domains, domain-specific analysis was not feasible. The standardization of all citations to IEEE format likely mitigated some domain-specific citation style variations, though residual side effects may still be present. Additionally, focusing on a single domain would simplify the recruitment of expert annotators with sufficient domain knowledge to accurately verify all citations, potentially leading to an overall higher annotation quality.

Several annotation attributes in this thesis relate to the *claims* within citation statements, defined as individually verifiable atomic statements [10]. Future research on citation verification would benefit from explicitly extracting these claims from citation statements,

following approaches used in the *SciFact* [10] and *SciClaimHunt* [11] datasets. However, claims should remain linked to their original sentences to enable the development of verification tools that can be directly applied to scientific texts. Such a dataset would also facilitate the training of a claim extraction component that could be integrated into the classification pipeline. The findings from this thesis indicate that verifying statements with multiple citations or multiple claims has a slight negative impact on classification performance, suggesting that verifying atomic claims separately could enhance overall accuracy.

Concurrently, the dataset created by Zhang and Abernethy [6] employs only one-to-one citation-reference mappings, despite many citations referencing multiple papers. An enhanced dataset should provide comprehensive information about all referenced papers, either as separate entries or within consolidated rows, to enable accurate verification of citation claims that draw evidence from multiple sources.

Apart from possible dataset enhancements, there are also pipeline implementation adjustments that might further increase the classification performance. While the method of extracting the textual information of the reference papers using *GROBID* was successful in most cases, the resulting *TEI* document structure contains a lot of tags with metadata that is not needed for this specific use case, for example detailed bibliography information or information on all authors and funders. Additionally, the *GROBID* text extraction had difficulties extracting complex text snippets like mathematical formulas. Information contained within tables and figures could also not be extracted by this tool, even though they could be highly relevant for substantiating citations. Due to time constraints, comparing multiple text extraction tools was not feasible within the scope of this thesis. However, future research should evaluate alternative extraction tools for *PDF* documents. One promising candidate is *olmOCR*³⁹, an open-source tool designed to convert *PDF* content containing sections, tables, and equations into linearized plain text while preserving the natural reading order [125].

Regarding the process of identifying the most relevant text excerpts of the reference paper, it could make sense to test out other text splitters from *LlamaIndex* for chunking, like the *SemanticSplitterNodeParser*, which takes embedding similarity of different sentences into consideration [99]. Alternatively, reference papers could be included in their entirety within the prompt rather than being segmented into chunks. While *LLMs* can struggle to identify relevant information in extensive prompts [95], the trend toward larger context windows in newer models [46, 53] presents new opportunities for comprehensive document processing. The configuration parameter analysis of this thesis demonstrates a clear performance differential which supports this potential: while older and smaller models

³⁹<https://olmocr.allenai.org/>

like GPT-3.5 exhibit reduced performance with larger chunk sizes (1,024 tokens vs. 256 tokens), the performance of the newer GPT-4.1 model is slightly increased with larger context length. The Llama 4 Scout model on the other hand performed significantly worse, despite its supposedly industry leading large context windows [53]. Nevertheless, future citation verification systems could potentially be enhanced by utilizing full document processing capabilities as model architectures further advance.

Additional improvements to the classification pipeline could be achieved through advanced prompt optimization strategies, such as implementing few-shot learning by incorporating labeled examples into the prompt or utilizing Chain-of-Thought (CoT) prompting to enhance reasoning capabilities. These strategies would also benefit from models with enhanced attention mechanisms designed for processing very long context windows.

Future research could explore newer reasoning models such as GPT-5, which demonstrate enhanced capabilities in scientific reasoning and complex problem-solving that could be applicable to the task of citation verification [57]. Choosing a suitable classifier LLM has a large impact on the classification performance, as demonstrated by the configuration parameter analysis of this thesis in section 6.2.2. The results reveal a balanced accuracy difference of 19.2% between the GPT-3.5 Turbo model and the GPT-4.1 model, using otherwise the same configuration (achieving the best overall metric value of 85.6% for GPT-4.1).

However, several limitations constrain the approach of using general-domain LLMs for automated citation verification. A significant concern stems from the enormous size of LLM training datasets, combined with intransparent training processes and undisclosed data sources. This creates uncertainty about which scientific papers were included in the training data. When verifying a citation statement against a specific source, it becomes unclear whether the LLM bases its classification solely on the provided text excerpts or draws upon parametric knowledge from similar papers or even the referenced paper itself that may have been encountered during training.

Additionally, the black-box nature of LLMs creates challenges when attempting to control the generated output in precise ways, such as ensuring compliance with exact formatting requirements. While many contemporary LLMs offer structured output capabilities that guarantee generated content conforms to predefined JSON formats [121], support for other structured formats remains limited.

A particularly challenging issue for classification tasks is the difficulty of achieving specific target quotas or coverage rates through prompt engineering alone. To explore this limitation, a supplementary experiment was conducted to investigate whether an LLM could serve as a selective classifier by filtering citations based solely on the citation statement

and task description without access to the reference paper. The experimental prompts and results are detailed in appendix section B.3.

This experiment demonstrated certain instabilities in LLM prompting: minor wording modifications in the prompts led to dramatic variations in selective coverage rates, ranging from as low as 34.82% to as high as 99.19%. For selective classification to be beneficial, it should primarily filter out misclassified citations while retaining correctly classified ones. Given the best achieved balanced accuracy of approximately 85%, a selective classifier should also maintain a coverage rate of at least 85%. However, achieving such precise coverage rates proves extremely challenging given the limited configurability of LLMs through prompt design alone.

In conclusion, while the significance analysis of this thesis in section 6.3 did not yield statistically significant results, notable patterns such as consistent performance declines for citations containing numbers or formulas suggest that syntactic and semantic features could influence LLM verification capabilities. Although the research question cannot be definitively answered due to the lack of statistical significance, the observed performance variations indicate that further research with larger datasets and refined methodologies would likely produce more conclusive findings.

Beyond addressing the primary research question, this thesis makes several important contributions to automated citation verification research. The developed annotation scheme provides a systematic framework for analyzing linguistic characteristics of citations, while the identification of dataset limitations offers concrete improvement suggestions. The demonstration that classification performance depends strongly on configuration parameters and LLM choice establishes essential groundwork for optimization strategies.

Overall, this work lays the foundation for developing real-world applicable automated citation verification tools and emphasizes the critical importance of scientific fact-checking in an era of widespread generative AI adoption.

Chapter 8

Conclusion

This thesis investigated the potential and limitations of zero-shot in-context learning for automated citation verification. The primary focus was examining how semantic and syntactic linguistic features of citation statements influence LLM classification performance. First, requirements for a suitable dataset were established, and the dataset created by Zhang and Abernethy [6] containing 250 citation-reference pairs was selected as it met these requirements, primarily because it was created for a similar research task and includes naturally occurring citation errors rather than artificially generated ones. The dataset underwent thorough review and enhancement to align with the research objectives. Key modifications included completing incomplete sentences, standardizing all citations to IEEE format while preserving originally excluded multiple references and citations, and manually reclassifying all Partially Substantiated citations as either Substantiated or Unsubstantiated. Additionally, an annotation scheme comprising six attributes was designed and applied to capture syntactic and semantic differences between citations that might potentially influence classification performance, based on prior research on LLM limitations. Subsequently, a classification pipeline was implemented following the architecture described by Zhang and Abernethy [6]. This pipeline automatically converts reference paper PDFs into textual TEI documents and retrieves the most relevant text chunks using word embedding similarity to generate classification prompts for the LLM classifier. Using both the original and re-annotated datasets, two grid searches were conducted to optimize the pipeline's configuration parameters. Among other optimizations, six LLM models were evaluated: four OpenAI GPT variants (GPT-3.5 Turbo, GPT-4.1 nano, GPT-4.1 mini, GPT-4.1) and two Meta Llama models (Llama 3.1 70B, Llama 4 Scout). Finally, classification results from the best-performing configuration were analyzed by grouping citations according to their annotation attribute values and comparing performance metrics across the resulting citation subsets. Several notable performance differences were observed that largely aligned with the initial assumptions regarding linguistic feature influences. For instance, citations containing numbers or mathematical formulas demonstrated approximately 8% lower performance across all evaluated metrics compared to the full dataset.

However, comprehensive statistical significance testing revealed that the observed differences lack statistical significance. While these differences may reflect random variation, they could also stem from methodological constraints: limited dataset size, overly conservative significance testing resulting from the large number of simultaneous comparisons, or an annotation scheme that may not adequately capture the most influential linguistic features.

In conclusion, the future success of **ICL** approaches using general-domain **LLMs** for specialized classification tasks like citation verification will require continued advancements in **LLM** capabilities alongside the development of more advanced domain-specific adaptation techniques. While the balanced accuracy of 85.6% achieved in this thesis demonstrates the promising potential of integrating **LLMs** into citation verification pipelines, it also highlights the need for substantial further research before such systems can be reliably deployed in real-world applications.

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Appendix A

Dataset and Annotation Examples

This appendix chapter contains three example sentences for each attribute value of the annotation attribute *Citation Sentence Structure* in section A.1, and a full example of a TEI document extracted with GROBID together with the extracted text from applying the PBTE component in section A.2.

A.1 *Citation Sentence Structure* Annotation Example Sentences

The following citation statements from the re-annotated dataset were selected to showcase examples of the different attribute values for the annotation attribute *Citation Sentence Structure*. Citations and references other than the reference paper number of the main citation are grayed out.

Simple:

“Others have aimed to reduce irreversibility or optimize energy-consumed devices [35, 36, 37, 38].” (*Citation ID*: cit001_1)

“Meng, Champion et al. [11] proposed a hybrid artificial bee colony algorithm.” (*Citation ID*: cit007_1)

“Global warming caused by excessive carbon dioxide pollution may be the most serious environmental problem [4].” (*Citation ID*: cit011_1)

Complex_Single-Clause:

“In the MDV, 1,000 km to the north and 1.8 km lower in elevation, cyanobacteria inhabit rocky soils [264], lake ice [265], and ice-covered hypersaline lakes [266, 267] in areas that rarely touch the melting point [268].” (*Citation ID*: cit065_1)

“Other investigations of Peptide5 in preclinical models have included elucidation of its salutary effects on retinal pigment epithelial cell barrier function

[107], diabetic retinopathy [108], and chronic kidney disease [109].” (*Citation ID: cit046_2*)

“Since 2D pose estimation of the 3D pose has deep uncertainty, according to the literature [16], the hybrid density network proposed by Bishop [17] can be used to estimate the prediction uncertainty.” (*Citation ID: cit010_1*)

Complex_Multiple_Clauses:

“In early studies, primary alkyl electrophiles were coupled with alkylmagnesium reagents (Grignard reagents) in the presence of transition-metal catalysts such as copper (Fig. 6A) [13, 14].” (*Citation ID: cit108_1*)

“The relative content of total flavonoids in the petroleum ether phase is the smallest, only (5.70 ± 10.19) mg/g, the relative content of total phenolic acid in the water phase is the smallest, which is (4.07 ± 10.94) mg/g [11].” (*Citation ID: cit002_1*)

“The second method is based on the traditional cartoon rendering algorithm [4, 5], which controls the ink texture mapping by designing a specific lighting function to achieve the ink style rendering effect, which is simple, realistic, and has good real-time performance.” (*Citation ID: cit022_1*)

A.2 TEI Document with Extracted Body Text Example

This section contains the with GROBID extracted TEI document and the corresponding result from the PBTE component for the shortest reference paper of the dataset: “Systematic reviews on rehabilitation interventions” by Handoll (DOI: 10.1016/j.apmr.2006.04.006).

A.2.1 Original TEI Document Structure

```

1 <?xml version="1.0" encoding="UTF-8"?>
2 <TEI xml:space="preserve" xmlns="http://www.tei-c.org/ns/1.0"
3 xmlns:xsi="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema-instance"
4 xsi:schemaLocation="http://www.tei-c.org/ns/1.0 https://raw.githubusercontent.com/kermitt2/grobid/master/grobid-home/schemas/xsd/Grobid.xsd"
5 xmlns:xlink="http://www.w3.org/1999/xlink">
6 <teiHeader xml:lang="en">
7 <fileDesc>
8 <titleStmt>
9 <title level="a" type="main"></title>

```

Appendix A Dataset and Annotation Examples

```
10 </titleStmt>
11 <publicationStmt>
12   <publisher/>
13   <availability status="unknown"><licence/></availability>
14 </publicationStmt>
15 <sourceDesc>
16   <biblStruct>
17     <analytic>
18       <author>
19         <persName><roleName>PT</roleName><forename type="first">Peter</
20           forename><surname>Van Der Wurff</surname></persName>
21         <affiliation key="aff0">
22           <orgName type="department">Div of Perioperative Medicine and
23             Emergency Medicine</orgName>
24           <orgName type="institution">University Medical Centre Utrecht
25             Utrecht</orgName>
26           <address>
27             <country key="NL">The Netherlands</country>
28           </address>
29         </affiliation>
30       </author>
31       <author>
32         <persName><roleName>PhD</roleName><forename type="first">Evert</
33           forename><forename type="middle">J</forename><surname>Buijs</
34           surname></persName>
35         <affiliation key="aff0">
36           <orgName type="department">Div of Perioperative Medicine and
37             Emergency Medicine</orgName>
38           <orgName type="institution">University Medical Centre Utrecht
39             Utrecht</orgName>
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42           </address>
43         </affiliation>
44       </author>
45       <author>
46         <persName><roleName>MD</roleName><forename type="first">Gerbrand</
47           forename><forename type="middle">J</forename><surname>Groen</
48           surname></persName>
49         <affiliation key="aff0">
50           <orgName type="department">Div of Perioperative Medicine and
51             Emergency Medicine</orgName>
52           <orgName type="institution">University Medical Centre Utrecht
53             Utrecht</orgName>
54           <address>
55             <country key="NL">The Netherlands</country>
56           </address>
57         </affiliation>
58       </author>
59     </analytic>
60   </biblStruct>
61 </sourceDesc>
62 </publicationStmt>
63 </title>
64 </text>
```

Appendix A Dataset and Annotation Examples

```
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47     </author>
48     </analytic>
49     <monogr>
50     <imprint>
51     <date/>
52     </imprint>
53     </monogr>
54     <idno type="MD5">B035E1E51242AB1EE27687E061EE85C2</idno>
55     </biblStruct>
56     </sourceDesc>
57 </fileDesc>
58 <encodingDesc>
59   <appInfo>
60     <application version="0.8.2" ident="GROBID" when="2025-07-02T08
61       :56+0000">
62       <desc>GROBID - A machine learning software for extracting information
63         from scholarly documents</desc>
64       <label type="revision">a91ee48</label>
65       <label type="parameters">startPage=-1, endPage=-1,
66         consolidateCitations=0, consolidateHeader=0, consolidateFunders=0,
67         includeRawAffiliations=false, includeRawCitations=false,
68         includeRawCopyrights=false, generateTeiIds=false,
69         generateTeiCoordinates=[], sentenceSegmentation=false, flavor=null
70     </label>
71     <ref target="https://github.com/kermitt2/grobid"/>
72   </application>
73 </appInfo>
74 </encodingDesc>
75 <profileDesc>
76   <abstract>
77 <div xmlns="http://www.tei-c.org/ns/1.0"><p>dispute this and agree that this
78   claim reflects generally accepted practice. However, the rationale of our
79   study was to investigate diagnostic accuracy by eliminating as much as
80   possible bias in the index test (provocation tests) as well as the
81   reference test (intra-articular sacroiliac joint [SIJ] blocks). Fritz and
82   Wainner 1 have stated that improper use of the reference standard in a
83   diagnostic study may compromise the validity of the research. In our
84   opinion, bias could be introduced in the study if after the first injection
85   a selection is made: 1 group consists of patients who react negatively and
86   decide not to accept a second injection and the other group reacts
87   positively and decides to receive the second (confirming) injection. This
88   will include recollection knowledge of the anesthesiologist and
89   investigator and that are dealing with a potential "positive" group.
90   Furthermore, patients have knowledge of the design of the study as a result
91   of the informed consent procedure and may be willing to react more
92   positively if they receive the second injection. Again, to overcome that
```

```

bias, in our (blinded) design, some of the patients received a second
injection, which could be regarded, in retrospect, as unnecessary, provided
the first block was negative.</p><p>Selection of patients eligible for
study purposes in relation to the SIJ is an actual issue. Laslett et al 2
combined the SIJ provocation test with the McKenzie procedure in a clinical
reasoning process to eliminate (separate) patients with intervertebral
disk problems from the patients suitable for an SIJ study population. In
our study, we withdrew patients with disk pathology based on magnetic
resonance imaging scans in combination with neurologic deficits. From a
purely clinical viewpoint, we can understand that their algorithm will work
in daily practice.</p><p>Regarding the comment of Laslett, Aprill, and
McDonald on false-positive rates, we agree that there is a lack of data on
the false-positive rate for the initial screening for the SIJ block.</p><p>
We thank Laslett and colleagues for their suggestion to publish the data as
such and will consider it in the near future.</p></div>
71 </abstract>
72 </profileDesc>
73 </teiHeader>
74 <text xml:lang="en">
75 <body>
76 <div xmlns="http://www.tei-c.org/ns/1.0"><head>Systematic Reviews on
Rehabilitation Interventions</head><p>I was impressed with the breadth of
Tate's lecture <ref type="bibr">1</ref> on the state of rehabilitation
research, which provided evidence of encouraging progress in this area.
However, the progress on the systematic reviewing of the rehabilitation
interventions is sadly rather more modest than she has reported. <ref type
="bibr">1</ref> Specifically, her reported number of 5075 Cochrane reviews
on rehabilitation for just 7 selected diagnostic groups in July 2005
exceeds the total of 2608 completed reviews in the Cochrane Database of
Systematic Reviews (Issue 1, 2006). It may well be that her search results
included "hits" from several of the other 7 databases also contained in the
Cochrane Library. A search purely on rehabilitation, as probably used by
Tate, yields 334 completed Cochrane reviews and 106 protocols for Cochrane
reviews in the Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews (Issue 1, 2006).
This simple search strategy will, however, miss several relevant reviews
and include other nonrehabilitation reviews.</p><p>Despite the far smaller
number of Cochrane reviews, Cochrane and other systematic reviews of
rehabilitation are still a growth area in terms of "number, scope, and
quality" as concluded by Tate. By virtue of their being updated on a
regular basis, Cochrane reviews are indeed particularly "valuable tools on
which to continue to build a strong theoretical body of knowledge." <ref
type="bibr">1(p164)</ref> However, there is still considerably more to be
done and, in particular, I urge rehabilitation specialists to contribute
actively to this endeavor.</p></div>
77 <div xmlns="http://www.tei-c.org/ns/1.0"><head>Helen H. Handoll, DPhil</head><p>
>University of Teesside Middlesbrough, UK h.handoll@tees.ac.uk</p></div>
</body>

```

Appendix A Dataset and Annotation Examples

```
78 <back>
79 <div type="references">
80
81 <listBibl>
82
83 <biblStruct xml:id="b0">
84 <analytic>
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86 perspective</title>
87 <author>
88 <persName><forename type="first">J</forename><forename type="middle">M</
89 forename><surname>Fritz</surname></persName>
90 </author>
91 <author>
92 <persName><forename type="first">R</forename><forename type="middle">S</
93 forename><surname>Wainner</surname></persName>
94 </author>
95 </analytic>
96 <monogr>
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98 <imprint>
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100 <biblScope unit="page" from="1546" to="1564" />
101 <date type="published" when="2001">2001</date>
102 </imprint>
103 </monogr>
104 </biblStruct>
105
106 <biblStruct xml:id="b1">
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108 <title level="a" type="main">Diagnosis of sacroiliac joint pain: validity
109 of individual provocation tests and composites of tests</title>
110 <author>
111 <persName><forename type="first">M</forename><surname>Laslett</surname></
112 persName>
113 </author>
114 <author>
115 <persName><forename type="first">C</forename><forename type="middle">N</
116 forename><surname>Aprill</surname></persName>
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118 <author>
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```

Appendix A Dataset and Annotation Examples

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131     <analytic>
132         <title level="a" type="main">The state of rehabilitation research: art or
133             science?</title>
134         <author>
135             <persName><forename type="first">D</forename><forename type="middle">G</
136                 forename><surname>Tate</surname></persName>
137         </author>
138         <idno type="DOI">10.1016/j.apmr.2006.04.006875</idno>
139     </analytic>
140     <monogr>
141         <title level="j">Arch Phys Med Rehabil</title>
142         <imprint>
143             <biblScope unit="volume">87</biblScope>
144             <biblScope unit="page" from="160" to="166" />
145             <date type="published" when="2006-06">2006. June 2006</date>
146         </imprint>
147     </monogr>
148     <note>Arch Phys Med Rehabil</note>
149 </biblStruct>
150
151 </listBibl>
152 </div>
153 </back>
154 </text>
155 </TEI>
```

A.2.2 Extracted Body Text

Systematic Reviews on Rehabilitation Interventions I was impressed with the breadth of Tate's lecture 1 on the state of rehabilitation research, which provided evidence of encouraging progress in this area. However, the progress on the systematic reviewing of the rehabilitation interventions is sadly rather more modest than she has reported. 1 Specifically, her reported number of 5075 Cochrane reviews on rehabilitation for just 7 selected diagnostic groups in July 2005 exceeds the total of 2608 completed reviews in the Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews (Issue 1, 2006). It may well be that her search results included "hits" from several of the other 7 databases also contained in the Cochrane Library. A search purely on rehabilitation, as probably used by Tate, yields 334 completed Cochrane reviews and 106 protocols for Cochrane reviews in the Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews (Issue 1, 2006). This simple search strategy will, however, miss several relevant reviews and include other nonrehabilitation reviews. Despite the far smaller number of Cochrane reviews, Cochrane and other systematic reviews of rehabilitation are still a growth area in terms of "number, scope, and quality" as concluded by Tate. By virtue of their being updated on a regular basis, Cochrane reviews are indeed particularly "valuable tools on which to continue to build a strong theoretical body of knowledge." 1(p164) However, there is still considerably more to be done and, in particular, I urge rehabilitation specialists to contribute actively to this endeavor.

Helen H. Handoll, DPhil University of Teesside Middlesbrough, UK h.handoll@tees.ac.uk

Appendix B

Prompt and LLM Response Examples

This appendix chapter provides a complete example of a generated classification prompt for the re-annotated dataset in section B.1 and examples of LLM classification responses with target labels and explanations in section B.2. Additionally, section B.3 presents the results of a short experimental series exploring the use of an LLM to classify the suitability of citation statements for automated citation verification.

B.1 Classification Prompt Example

The following prompt was generated based on one dataset row. The reference text excerpts resulted from 256 token chunking with 20 token overlap using the IndexLlama *Sentence-Splitter*, embedding using the OpenAI *text-embedding-3-large* embedding and retrieving the top 3 most similar chunks to the statement.

You are an experienced scientific writer and editor. You will be given a citation statement from an article that cites a reference article. From this same reference article you will receive the additional information, including the title, the abstract of the article and the top 3 most relevant excerpts from the reference article. The relevance of the excerpts was previously determined by another large language model based on the citation statement.

Your task is to determine and explain if the reference article supports the given citation statement.

The statement sentence can contain multiple citations and can refer to multiple reference articles, which are all cited in IEEE style. You are given the number of the reference article that you should check (“Reference Number”). When for example the statement is “X is true [37, 38] and Y is false under certain conditions [39]”, and you are given the reference number 37, you should only check the first part of the statement that refers to the reference article 37.

As your classification result, decide between the two labels “Substantiated” and “Unsubstantiated”. Further explanations of the labels are as follows:

“Substantiated”: The reference article fully substantiates the relevant part of the presented citation statement. This means that only based on the information from the reference article, the statement does not contain errors and can be considered correct.

“Unsubstantiated”: The reference article does not substantiate the relevant part of the presented citation

statement. This could be because the statement is contradictory to, unrelated to, or simply missing from the reference article. All of these options would indicate that the citation is incorrect based on the cited references.

Format your answer in JSON with two elements: “label” and “explanation”. Your explanation should be short and concise.

The citing article

– Title: Nanodiamonds suppress the growth of lithium dendrites

– Statement: Aggregation of nanodiamond particles cannot be fully avoided in the electrolyte and nanodiamond clusters with a size of 530 nm were measured by dynamic light scattering (Fig. 1e). This size of nanodiamond clusters was largely reduced compared to the pristine commercial nanodiamond [39].

The reference article

– Reference Number: 39

– Title: Deagglomeration and functionalisation of detonation nanodiamond with long alkyl chains

– Abstract: We have achieved the covalent functionalisation of detonation nanodiamond by an esterification reaction of carboxylic acid chlorides on hydroxylated nanodiamond. The resulting “nanodiamond esters” with a surface loading of 0.3-0.4 mmol g⁻¹ of alkyl groups have been characterized by FTIR spectroscopy, thermogravimetry and elemental analysis. They exhibit a significantly improved dispersibility in organic solvents such as tetrahydrofuran and dichloromethane.

– Excerpts:

Excerpt 1: Introduction Diamond nanoparticles have found considerable interest recently due to their potential applications in biological systems, composites and electronic applications [1]. Their apparent biocompatibility [2] and chemical inertness make them an ideal candidate for all kinds of biomedical devices. On the other hand, their surface can be functionalised with a variety of groups in order to incorporate them into polymer matrices, surface coatings and the like [3]. An essential prerequisite for these applications is the control of surface structure and particle size and agglomeration. So far, different approaches for the surface functionalisation and deagglomeration have been taken. Chiganova produced diamond hydrosols from oxidized detonation diamond [4], whereas Xu and coworkers used surface active compounds for the dispersion of nanodiamond particles [5]. Khabashesku et al. obtained small agglomerates of 160 nm in size by the fluorination of detonation diamond [6]. These particles formed stable suspensions in THF. Another approach is the mechanical deagglomeration in suspension by stirred media milling [7] or beads assisted sonic disintegration [8].

Excerpt 2: In the latter solvent no sedimentation was observed for a period of one month. The particle size of the agglomerates in the suspensions was reduced from several micron (pristine ND: 15

micrometers, ND-OH: 6 micrometers) to 300-450 nm in the case of ND-OOC-C 3 H 7 (2), 150-260 nm for ND-OOC-C 5 H 11 (3), 170 nm for ND-OOC-C 12 H 23 (4), and 170-300 nm for ND-OOC-C 18 H 37 (5). Fig. 3 shows the development of suspensions of pristine detonation diamond and compounds 1-5 in dichloromethane. The stable dispersion of functionalised nanodiamond in organic solvents opens the way to further surface modification in more homogeneous systems leading to better accessibility of the surface groups as well as a more homogeneous distribution of the diamond particles in the medium. Carboxylic groups with terminal surface groups have to be reacted with the diamond surface if further reactions are to be carried out. This work is under way and will be reported elsewhere.

Excerpt 3: This work is under way and will be reported elsewhere. Conclusion In summary we have modified the surface of hydroxylated detonation nanodiamond with alkyl chains of different length by an esterification reaction of carboxylic acid chlorides with the surface hydroxyl groups. The resulting materials had a surface loading of 0.3-0.4 mmol g⁻¹ and showed a much better dispersibility in several organic solvents along with a smaller particle size of the remaining agglomerates. This enables the homogeneous incorporation of such materials in non-hydrophilic matrices and further modification in stable suspension. In the future, it will be important to further reduce the agglomerate size by such chemical deagglomeration and stabilization techniques down to the primary particles.

B.2 Examples for LLM Classification Responses with Explanations

This section contains correct and incorrect classification results from the best performing GPT-4.1 model using the best overall parameter configuration (1024 token chunk size, *SentenceSplitter*, *text-embedding-3-large*, with PBTE). Additionally, it contains an example of an ill-structured Llama 4 Scout response (using the same configuration).

B.2.1 GPT-4.1: Correct Classification of Substantiated Citation

Citation Paper:

Vertically extensive and unstable magmatic systems: A unified view of igneous processes (DOI: [10.1126/science.aag3055](https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aag3055))

Citation Statement:

“At very high crystallinities (very low melt permeabilities), gas-generated overpressures can fracture and brecciate the solidifying mush [125].” (Citation ID: cit055_1)

Target Label: Substantiated

Classification Label: Substantiated

Explanation:

The reference article discusses how gas (volatile fluid) overpressure can develop in a solidifying crystal pile when exsolved fluids cannot escape due to low permeability, leading

to sufficient overpressure to fracture and brecciate the mush, as observed in the formation of a breccia pipe. This directly supports the statement that at very high crystallinities (very low melt permeabilities), gas-generated overpressures can fracture and brecciate the solidifying mush.

B.2.2 GPT-4.1: Correct Classification of Unsubstantiated Citation

Citation Paper:

The social neuroscience of music: Understanding the social brain through human song (DOI: [10.1037/amp0000819](https://doi.org/10.1037/amp0000819))

Citation Statement:

“We know that oxytocin is released when listening to music, and importantly, oxytocin is increased when participating in several forms of group singing, including improvisation [1].” (*Citation ID*: cit045_1)

Target Label: Unsubstantiated

Classification Label: Unsubstantiated

Explanation:

The reference article reports that salivary oxytocin concentrations were significantly reduced after choir (group) singing and did not change after solo singing, directly contradicting the citation statement that oxytocin is increased when participating in group singing. The article’s findings challenge the view that group singing elevates oxytocin and instead suggest a reduction, making the citation unsubstantiated.

B.2.3 GPT-4.1: Incorrect Classification of Substantiated Citation

Citation Paper:

Cell Therapy for Anal Sphincter Incontinence: Where Do We Stand? (DOI: [10.3390/cells10082086](https://doi.org/10.3390/cells10082086))

Citation Statement:

“Most often, an anal sphincter tear is usually identified after delivery and surgically repaired [49].” (*Citation ID*: cit047_1)

Target Label: Substantiated

Classification Label: Unsubstantiated

Explanation:

The reference article states that injury to the anal sphincters, mainly post-surgical or post-delivery, is the most common cause of incontinence, and that surgical repair is actually the

treatment of choice. This directly supports the citation statement that anal sphincter tears are usually identified after delivery and surgically repaired.

B.2.4 GPT-4.1: Incorrect Classification of Unsubstantiated Citation

Citation Paper:

Nanodiamonds suppress the growth of lithium dendrites (DOI: [10.1038/s41467-017-00519-2](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-017-00519-2))

Citation Statement:

“Li columns with a small average diameter ($0.3 \sim 0.4 \mu\text{m}$) were obtained in the nanodiamond-containing electrolyte (Fig. 2h, Supplementary Fig. 5e, f), leading to a dendrite-free morphology [40].” (Citation ID: cit085_2)

Target Label: Unsubstantiated

Classification Label: Substantiated

Explanation:

The citation statement claims that Li columns with a small average diameter ($0.3 \sim 0.4 \mu\text{m}$) were obtained in a nanodiamond-containing electrolyte, leading to a dendrite-free morphology. However, the reference article discusses dendrite-free lithium deposition and small Li deposit sizes (100-300 nm) in a 3D fibrous Li₇B₆ matrix anode, not in a nanodiamond-containing electrolyte. There is no mention of nanodiamonds or the specific Li column diameters cited in the statement. Thus, the reference does not substantiate the statement.

B.2.5 Llama 4 Scout: Example of Ill-Structured Response

Citation Paper:

The social neuroscience of music: Understanding the social brain through human song (DOI: [10.1037/amp0000819](https://doi.org/10.1037/amp0000819))

Citation Statement:

“We know that oxytocin is released when listening to music, and importantly, oxytocin is increased when participating in several forms of group singing, including improvisation [1].” (Citation ID: cit045_1)

Target Label: Unsubstantiated

Model Response:

```
## Classification Result
The classification result for the given citation is:
### Substantiated
## Explanation
The reference article by Kreutz et al. (2014) presents findings that contradict the statement that oxytocin levels increase during choir singing. Instead, the study reveals that salivary oxytocin levels actually decrease during choir singing.
The study investigated the effects of choir singing on oxytocin and cortisol levels in healthy individuals. The results showed that choir singing led to a significant decrease in salivary oxytocin levels, whereas solo singing resulted in a slight increase.
These findings suggest that the statement “oxytocin levels increase during choir singing” is not supported by the evidence presented in the reference article.
## Classification
The classification result is therefore: **Substantiated**
However, it seems that the reference does not support the claim. Therefore, I reclassified it as:
The classification result for the given citation is:
### Unsubstantiated
## Explanation
The reference article by Kreutz et al. (2014) presents findings that contradict the statement that oxytocin levels increase during choir singing. Instead, the study reveals that salivary oxytocin levels actually decrease during choir singing.
The study investigated the effects of choir singing on oxytocin and cortisol levels in healthy individuals. The results showed that choir singing led to a significant decrease in salivary oxytocin levels, whereas solo singing resulted in a slight increase.
These findings suggest that the statement “oxytocin levels increase during choir singing” is not supported by the evidence presented in the reference article.
## Classification
The classification result is therefore: **Unsubstantiated**
```

B.3 Using an LLM as a Selective Classifier Function to Filter for Suitable Citations

This additional short experiment series was performed to test whether an LLM could be used to filter citation statements for their suitability for being classified in a zero-shot in-context learning setting. The prompt states the classification task of citation verification similarly to the classification prompt shown in section B.1, but only gives information on the citation itself (citation statement and citation paper title) and not on the reference paper. The GPT-4.1 model was prompted for each citation separately (without keeping the conversation context) using the following prompt template (based on one exemplary dataset row):

You are an expert at understanding the capabilities and limitations of large language models, especially in the context of text classification tasks. Your task is to determine and explain if a classifier LLM would be capable to successfully verify whether a reference article supports a given citation statement.

The classifier LLM will be given a citation statement from an article that cites a reference article. From this same reference article it will receive the additional information, including the title, the abstract of the article and the top 3 most relevant excerpts from the reference article. The relevance of the excerpts was previously determined by another large language model based on the citation statement. The statement sentence can contain multiple citations and can refer to multiple reference articles, which are all cited in IEEE style. The classifier LLM is given the number of the reference article that it should check (“Reference Number”). When for example the statement is “X is true [37, 38] and Y is false under certain conditions [39]”, and the LLM is given the reference number 37, it should only check the first part of the statement that refers to the reference article 37.

As the classification result, the classifier LLM should decide between the two labels “Substantiated” and “Unsubstantiated”. Further explanations of the labels are as follows: “Substantiated”: The reference article fully substantiates the relevant part of the presented citation statement. This means that only based on the information from the reference article, the statement does not contain errors and can be considered correct. “Unsubstantiated”: The reference article does not substantiate the relevant part of the presented citation statement. This could be because the statement is contradictory to, unrelated to, or simply missing from the reference article. All of these options would indicate that the citation is incorrect based on the cited references.

You should evaluate if the following citation statement is suited to be correctly classified by a classifier LLM, using your knowledge on the limitations of large language models. You do not get any of the information on the reference article so that you can focus on the characteristics of the citation itself. Please (only) answer “No” if there are (strong / any) indications that the citation is not suited (because your response will be used to perform a selective classification) .

(The selective classification coverage should be at around 85%.)

Format your answer in the following JSON format:

```
{
  "citation suited": "Yes"/"No" (based on your decision),
  "explanation": <reasoning for your decision>
}
```

Your explanation should be short and concise.

The citing article

– Title: Nanodiamonds suppress the growth of lithium dendrites

– Statement: Aggregation of nanodiamond particles cannot be fully avoided in the electrolyte and nan-

odiamond clusters with a size of 530 nm were measured by dynamic light scattering (Fig. 1e). This size of nanodiamond clusters was largely reduced compared to the pristine commercial nanodiamond [39].

Four different prompts with small variations were tested out to measure how effective the selective classification coverage rate can be influenced via the prompt. The prompt either asks the LLM to only classify citations with strong indications as not suitable or to classify citations with any indications as not suitable (together with the small additional adjustments marked as orange or blue respectively). Additionally, the prompt either does include information on the expected selective classification rate or leaves this information out (marked with green).

The results of this experiment are displayed in table B.1.

Table B.1: Citation suitability classification results for prompting the GPT-4.1 model with the four different prompt variants, showing the amounts of citations labelled as “suited” and “not suited” and the resulting selective classification coverage rate

Coverage Info	Indication Level	Suited	Not Suited	Coverage
No coverage info	Strong indications	245	2	0.9919
	Any indications	95	152	0.3846
Fixed coverage	Strong indications	244	3	0.9879
	Any indications	86	161	0.3482